

**JUST
WIND
4 ALL**

T3.2 NORTH HOLLAND REGIONAL REPORT

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Description	A review of the development of wind energy governance in the Dutch province of North Holland focusing on the period 2013-2023. Specific attention is paid to the actor constellations involved in wind energy governance, the role of citizens, the procedures around site selection, and how aspects of justice are understood in policies.

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DISCLAIMER AND FORWARD

This case study about wind energy developments in North Holland, the Netherlands, has been produced for the Horizon Europe JustWind4All (JW4A) project as part of WP3 task 3.2. The task aims to develop an understanding of regional challenges and opportunities around wind energy governance over the past 5-10 years to formulate key recommendations to foster energy citizenship through effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is based on a mixed method approach including for each region: document reviews (around 50), 5-10 interviews with wind energy governance actors and a media and policy analysis. A comparative analysis across cases and the project's regions allows for a better understanding of challenges and opportunities around effective and just wind energy governance.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 COUNTRY CONTEXT

The Netherlands, renowned for its innovative use of windmills to manage water levels in its low-lying landscape since the 11th century, has a rich history of energy development. Over time, the country has become a leader in installed wind capacity, with ambitious targets cut out for the coming decades. However, despite its favourable wind conditions and long-standing wind energy heritage, the country faces unique challenges due to its high population density and limited available space, particularly for further onshore wind development. This intricate balance between historical wind energy usage and modern challenges shapes the country's energy context, with wind energy playing a pivotal role in its cultural identity and renewable energy transition.

1.1.1 THE DUTCH ENERGY SYSTEM

The modern Dutch energy mix can be characterised by the discovery of the vast Groningen gas field in the late 1950s, which led to a rapid transition away from the previously dominant peat- and coal-based energy mix to one dominated by natural gas (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018). Led by the Netherlands Petroleum Company (NL: Nederlands Aardolie Maatschappij; NAM), extraction from the gas fields commenced in the 1960s. NAM, with Shell and Exxon as shareholders, held the Dutch monopoly on Dutch natural gas mining during this time. This resulted in the swift growth of natural gas, which surged to represent 80% of the Dutch electricity sector by the mid-1970s, and defied an era dominated by a highly centralized and inflexible energy system. During this period, there was a prevailing perception of energy abundance, influencing the stability of energy prices (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018). The onset of the global oil crisis in the mid-1970s swiftly halted this period of abundance and encouraged the Netherlands to look beyond gas to supply its energy-related needs. Nuclear energy and renewable energy sources entered into the public eye, and the first efforts towards implementing these sources occurred over the following decade (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018; van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020a). After the European liberalisation of the energy market in the late 1990s, the Dutch energy landscape opened up to decentralised, smaller-scale energy producers, and renewable energy became an established player in the energy mix (see Figure 1). The 2013 Dutch Energy Agreement (Energieakkoord) set national standards for renewable energy plans, accelerating development in many areas of the country (IEA, 2020a). This was followed up by the 2019 Climate Agreement (Klimaatakkoord), which introduced a new approach to onshore renewable energy planning and governance and introduced ambitious plans for offshore wind in the North Sea.

Liberalisation of the energy market

However, since the liberalisation of the energy market, the energy system has become predominantly market-driven, with little national government intervention (Kooij, Lagendijk, et al., 2018). Network operators, while local or national governments are part shareholders, are most often driven through commercial activities. While market liberalisation has allowed for the emergence of smaller and decentralised energy producers (often renewable energy cooperatives), these groups struggle to compete against a system that is still set up to favour market giants (Agterbosch & Breukers, 2008; Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018). However, some measures are in place to encourage local renewable energy cooperatives, such as the 2013 Postcode Catchment Area (NL: *postcoderoos*) ruling. This allowed tax deductions for those living in an area wherein electricity is generated cooperatively.

Thereby, it stimulated local electricity generation and aimed to reduce local opposition against energy projects through financial benefits.

Figure 1. Total energy supply (TES) of the Netherlands by source, 1990-2020, source: (IEA, 2022).

Ambitious renewable targets and dominance of fossil fuels

Despite the historic reliance on natural gas, the Netherlands now seeks to diversify its energy mix and increase its share of renewable energy sources. In 2021, renewables accounted for approximately 13% of energy production, with wind energy emerging as a critical component of the transition (CBS, 2022). Nevertheless, coal, natural gas, and oil still heavily dominate the energy mix. The government has set ambitious targets for both on- and offshore renewable energy, with regions working collaboratively to meet a collective electricity production goal by 2030, and numerous offshore wind parks planned for the coming years (Ministerie van Algemene Zaken, 2022).

Delays in renewable: opposition and consensus-driven ‘polder’ governance

However, reaching renewable energy goals has proven challenging, as the Netherlands has lagged behind many other EU member states in the adoption of renewables (Klok et al., 2023). As of 2021, the country ranked third-to-last in terms of final energy consumption sourced from renewable sources, and well below the EU average of approximately 22% (13% in the Netherlands) (Eurostat, 2023).

While there is strong overall public support for renewable energy, local opposition to wind energy projects has slowed down the rollout (Koelman et al., 2022). Arguably playing a role in this is the ‘polder’ governance model which characterises the Netherlands (Aarts et al., 2022). A ‘polder’ refers to residential and rural lands that have been reclaimed from the sea, keeping nearly one-third of the country that lies under sea level afloat. The process of ‘poldering’ mirrors the country’s consensus-driven governance, characterized by broad coalitions involving various civil society actors. Such a governance model also extends to energy transition strategies, where dialogues and agreements with stakeholders pave the way for legislative moves in the energy sector.

1.1.2 WIND ENERGY DEVELOPMENT IN THE NETHERLANDS

A long history of wind energy

The Netherlands has a long history of wind energy development, which has ramped up since the oil crisis in the 1970s. Dutch citizens form a central part of this history, with wind cooperatives emerging in the 1980s, and were already well established by the turn of the century compared to citizen initiatives in neighbouring countries (van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020a). A wind energy cooperative can be defined as a self-governing group of citizens who form a decentralised, non-governmental initiative which produces wind energy (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018). As of 2022, there were 705 energy cooperatives registered in the Netherlands, within which 87 cooperatives were actively working on wind energy projects (“Lokale Energie Monitor 2022,” 2023).

High level of citizen engagement: protest and support

Aside from cooperatives, wind energy development is characterized by a **high degree of citizen engagement in projects**, both in terms of support and resistance. While the Netherlands has ideal conditions for wind energy development, the country’s high population density and history of frequent citizen contestations against onshore wind development renders **spatial planning** a point of contention.

Policy processes stimulating wind energy development

In addition to these social considerations, several major policy developments have influenced the progress of wind energy development over the past two decades, including European, national, and regional policies. An overview of notable policies from all three levels can be found in Figure 2. In addition, an overview of the governance levels which shaped these policies can be found Table 1.

In the period between 2013 and 2015, various levels of government introduced policies to increase the percentage of renewables in the Dutch energy mix. The signing of the **Paris Agreement** in 2015 specified a 2020 goal of 20-14-20: 20% increase in energy savings, 14% increase in renewable raw materials, 20% emissions reduction, all by 2020 (Van der Veen, 2014). The **2013 Energy Agreement** can be considered the foundational policy for wind energy goals during this period, with each province assigned a target for installed onshore wind energy by 2020. This placed the focus of onshore wind energy development in the hands of provincial governments, who had diverging approaches, resulting in various levels of success across the country. In addition, the Energy Agreement redefined the procedure for offshore wind tenders, with a focus on streamlining and increasing power in the hands of the national government instead of the developer. In addition, it defined a goal of 4.7 GW of offshore wind capacity by 2023 (IEA, 2020a). The Structural Vision Onshore Wind (SvWOL; Structuurvisie Wind op Land) in 2014 defined a goal of 6 GW of installed capacity of onshore wind by 2020 (Evers et al., 2019). These targets marked the first instance of concrete national goal-setting for wind energy. Of the targets, only the offshore wind target for 2023 was met and surpassed, with 4.7 GW of installed capacity by the end of 2023 (Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2023). An analysis by the Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency (NL: Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving, PBL) reflected that tools for rapid upscaling such as clear role divisions amongst government levels were missing from regional governments, and participation and consumer knowledge of onshore wind was lacking, which hindered progress (Evers et al., 2019). Nevertheless, the policies were effective in growing wind energy development both on and offshore, as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Installed capacity and targets for wind energy development in the Netherlands (sources: (Evers et al., 2019; Statistiek, 2021, 2023).

The next round of policy change is concentrated between 2019 and 2023, kicked off by the 2019 Climate Agreement. It aims for a 49% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030, and 95% by 2050 (IEA, 2020a). It also set a target for 15 TWh of installed capacity in onshore wind and solar in 2030. To implement this goal, a new governance level was created: 30 Regional Energy Strategy (RES) regions. Each province was split up into 2-3 RES regions, which became the new stewards of devising and implementing renewable energy plans (*National Climate Agreement The Netherlands*, 2019). With a bottom-up and participatory approach, each region sets its targets and must devise ‘search areas’ (NL: zoekgebieden) where renewable energy development ought to be installed. The creation of the RES regions shifts the decision-making power away from the province and towards municipalities, who vote to approve search areas within their boundaries. In addition, the RES plans aim to include a range of local stakeholders, including citizens and local businesses, in designating search areas (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). The initial plans from each region were published in 2020, and an updated version of the search areas was published in 2021-2022.

The Climate Agreement introduced a new offshore wind goal of 11.5 GW of installed capacity by 2030 (*New Offshore Wind Energy Roadmap*, 2022). The Climate Agreement was introduced concurrently with the EU-mandated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP), which each member state was required to draft. However, this is roughly identical to the Climate Agreement, although it specifies a renewable energy target of 27% of the energy supply by 2030 for the Netherlands (IEA, 2020a).

While the Climate Agreement already set ambitious targets for offshore wind, targets have ramped up drastically between 2019 and 2023. In 2020, the European Commission published the Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy (OWER), which set the direction of offshore wind development from 2020 to 2050 (European Commission, 2020). The North Sea area was highlighted as the leading area for development, with a push for member states to upscale more rapidly than planned. In response to

the OWER and a growing public rejection of onshore wind, the Dutch parliament nearly doubled the Climate Agreement offshore wind goals to 21 GW by 2030 instead of 11.5 GW (*New Offshore Wind Energy Roadmap*, 2022). As of 2020, the EU member states' goals for offshore wind energy totalled 90 GW of installed capacity by 2050 (European Commission, 2020). Thus, a goal of 21 GW by 2030 positions the Netherlands as a European leader in offshore wind. An overview of the planned Dutch wind parks can be seen in Figure 3. In contrast to onshore wind, which is regulated regionally and locally, offshore wind energy falls under the jurisdiction of the national government.

Figure 3. Offshore Wind Energy Roadmap for the North Sea of the Netherlands.

Alongside this increasing trend towards offshore wind, 2022 marked an EU-wide boost in efforts towards upscaling renewable energy. The invasion of Ukraine highlighted the fragile dependence on Russian fossil fuels for many EU member states, which pushed governments towards expanding domestic energy sources. The REPowerEU plan reflected this movement by increasing the EU renewable energy target (as a share of the energy supply) from 40% to 45% by 2050, although wind energy is not specifically addressed (European Commission, 2022).

Despite targets, onshore wind development remains a polarising issue in the Netherlands. With a large population and limited land, the Netherlands is short on space, warranting an in-depth investigation into wind energy governance and justice in the Netherlands. A recent study by Klok et al. (2023) attempted to identify suitable areas for wind energy developments in the Netherlands while considering constraints of geographical suitability, nuisance (shadow flicker, sound, visual, etc.), and land use including protected areas. Results estimated that the remaining potential for onshore wind energy exceeds national targets, with key development areas located in the north of the country (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Identified locations for wind energy development within the Netherlands based on locations with any suitability score (left) or with suitability scores high enough to meet industry standards for wind park approval only, excluding protected or restricted areas (right) by Klok et al., 2023). Suitable areas are shown in black.

1.2 REGIONAL CONTEXT

1.2.1 CASE STUDY SELECTION

As demonstrated in Figure 4, wind development suitability is concentrated in the North of the Netherlands. One northern province of particular interest is North Holland (see Figure 5). North Holland is a province in the northwest of the Netherlands. It contains two RES regions: North Holland North (NHN; Noord-Holland Noord) and North Holland South (NHS; Noord-Holland Zuid). At the south end of the province lies the capital city of the Netherlands, Amsterdam, with nearly one million residents. The province has nearly two million residents, meaning approximately half of the population is concentrated within the municipality of Amsterdam. This results in a stark divide between an urban epicentre in the province, and largely rural and agricultural areas making up the remainder.

Figure 5. Map of the Regional Energy Strategy Regions of the Netherlands, with the two RES regions of North Holland (ArcGIS Hub, 2023).

In the context of wind energy development, North Holland is notable for its long history with modern wind turbines in comparison to other provinces, as well as high public opposition to onshore wind in recent years (van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020a). While onshore wind flourished in the region around the turn of the century, public and political opposition led to a stalling of new onshore project approval in the 2010s. Despite these setbacks, the province ranks 4th out of the 12 Dutch provinces in installed capacity of onshore wind (see Figure 6). The province also contains the largest onshore wind park in the Netherlands to date, which is a particularly notable case due to its drawn-out planning process and series of contestations from local residents (Soeters, 2019). In addition, North Holland's extensive coastline provides for ideal offshore wind conditions, and several offshore wind parks are operating or planned off the coast of the province: Hollandse Kust (Noord) and IJmuiden Ver in the North Sea,

and a wind park in the IJsselmeer (see Figure 3). While the sea is not divided by province, offshore wind parks have an impact on the adjacent coast as establishing a connection to the electricity grid is necessary, in addition to their visual presence which often results in local deliberation (“Aansluiting Tennet Voor...,” 2023). Together, the strong presence of wind energy and the deep socio-cultural history surrounding it render North Holland a suitable case study for further investigation.

Figure 6. Installed capacity of onshore wind energy at the end of each year in the top four wind-energy-producing regions of the Netherlands. Source: CBS StatLine, 2023.

1.2.2 REGIONAL DEMARCATION

As one of the 12 provinces of the Netherlands, several governance levels are at play in wind energy development in North Holland. Table 1 provides an overview of the role of each level. While the provincial and municipal governments undergo four-year election cycles, the RES regions are directed by a self-appointed advisory board, which is comprised of a civil servant from each municipality-group, representatives from the network operator (Liander), environmental organisations, local energy cooperatives, and the water boards (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). The advisory board, in consultation with numerous local stakeholders, determines the value-based approach taken and proposes search areas to be voted upon by municipal councils. This has sparked political and public debate over the role of onshore wind within the province, with wind currently comprising about 10% of RES plans.

As for discrepancies between the two RES regions in North Holland, the regions have opted to take a nearly identical approach in terms of values, documentation, and communication strategy. The regions differ in terms of their quantitative goals for wind and solar development, with NHN aiming for 3.6 TWh of installed renewable energy capacity by 2030, and NHS for 2.7 TWh (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). However, relative to the current installed capacity, NHN plans to install 1.5 TWh of additional capacity, and NHS plans to install 2 additional TWh. This indicates that

development in the coming years will be concentrated in the more densely populated NHS, which has historically seen less wind energy growth in comparison to the rural northern part of the province. The governance structure and actions of the RES regions are further detailed in Section 4.4.

1.2.3 TEMPORAL DEMARCATION

For this case study, a pre-period of 1970-2012 was selected, with the oil crisis in the 1970s marking the start of wind energy entering the Dutch energy system, albeit remaining in the research and development phase until the 1990s. The pre-period aims to provide important historical context which informs more recent developments. In addition, a focus period of **2013 to 2023** was selected. The focus period aims to develop an in-depth understanding of recent evolutions and the factors which shaped them.

The policy overview in section 1.2 shows that from a policy perspective, the 2019 Climate Agreement may be a useful starting point for our focus period. However, upon further research, the starting point of the Climate Agreement can be traced back to the 2013 Energy Agreement. It is therefore insightful to start in 2013 to fully understand the context which led to the Climate Agreement. In addition, zooming in on North Holland, the years between 2013 and 2019 represent an important time frame when wind development was stagnating in North Holland due to public opposition and strict provincial regulations. Following the election of an anti-wind-energy coalition in the 2011 provincial elections, the coalition attempted to ban new wind energy development in the province in 2012, which was only fully repealed in 2020 (Van de Veen, 2014). Nevertheless, wind energy initiatives were heavily stifled by the province until the restructuring of the provincial environmental regulations in 2020, which mandated compliance with the RES. Therefore, the inclusion of the years between the Energy Agreement and Climate Agreement introduces valuable insights into the relevant developments that influence the current state of wind energy in North Holland today.

1.3 FOCUSING ON TWO INSTANCES OF PARTICIPATION

The selection of two instances of participation was challenging given the wide range of examples in the focus period in North Holland. The two instances were selected based on the scale of their impacts as well as their uniqueness to the Dutch context, both demonstrating good practices and situations to avoid. Firstly, the case of the Princesses Ariane Wind Park, better known as the Wieringermeer Wind Park, was selected. This is the largest onshore wind park to date in the Netherlands and received a great deal of public opposition over its 10-year greenlight to grid-connected time span (Soeters, 2019). Debates of justice were at the forefront of this opposition due to the construction of nearby data centres. Hence, it is a worthy case for further investigation. In addition, the debate and formation of the initial Regional Energy Strategy (RES) plan in North Holland resulted in the submission of two notable alternative proposals. These proposals were discussed and later incorporated into the final draft of RES plans in 2021. These occurrences are notable for their public engagement and constructive participation by local residents and stakeholders in a bottom-up planning process.

Table 1. Overview of governance levels and jurisdiction in onshore and offshore wind energy development in North Holland as of 2020 (IEA, 2020a; Koelman et al., 2022; "Tijdljn," 2020; van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020).

Governance level	Role	Onshore wind	On- and offshore wind	Offshore wind
European Union	<i>Influencing</i>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Drafts binding directives for wind energy targets and ambitions across the EU member states - Sets environmental regulations - Provides financial support through subsidies and research grants (such as JustWind4All) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitates cross-country collaboration on projects, such as in the North Sea area
Dutch government (Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate)	<i>Supervising</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jurisdiction over onshore wind projects > 100 MW - Sets national regulations for onshore wind (i.e. distance from dwellings, etc) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Defines national energy policy, in line with EU targets - Supervises progress of lower governance levels towards national/EU targets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Full jurisdiction over offshore wind park planning and strong influence in tendering process
Council of State (Raad van State)	<i>Regulating</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Final say in disputes over and legal objections to projects 		
Province of North Holland	<i>Coordinating</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinating role between RES regions, municipalities, and the province itself - Jurisdiction over spatial planning - Jurisdiction over wind parks between 5 MW and 100 MW - Provides funding for energy cooperative subsidy schemes - Sets provincial regulations for onshore wind (can override national regulations) 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitates spatial planning for connecting offshore wind parks to onshore grid
2 RES regions (North Holland North & South)	<i>Steering</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Defines targets and ratio of wind/solar for 2030 - Determines approach to development: participation, justice, other principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Steering role in the narrative of the energy transition (including on/offshore, solar, hydrogen, heat pumps, etc) 	
44 Municipalities	<i>Concretising</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Translates RES goals and search area into concrete projects - Jurisdiction over wind turbines < 5 MW - Voting power for approving/rejecting RES plans within municipality 		

1.4 AIMS AND REPORT STRUCTURE

This case study traces the development of wind energy governance in North Holland over a time span of 2013-2023. It zooms in on participation in social actions and processes for or against wind energy and outlines how these actions and processes are co-shaped by regulations, discourses, and norms over time. Doing so allows for the highlighting of regional challenges and opportunities for wind energy governance. This report is one out of a set of seven case study reports that together provide insights for the formulation of key recommendations to foster energy citizenship through effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is in this way that it connects to JW4A's ambition of understanding **how wind energy governance can become more just and effective**.

Specifically, this report provides a historical understanding of the interplay between diverse types of actors around wind energy development in North Holland. At the heart of this report is an overview of the historical narrative of how wind energy governance developed in North Holland along three phases: (1) Governments take the lead, (2) National ambitions, local engagement, (3) Energy security and offshore ambitions (see Section 4). Each of these phases is connected to at least one critical instance of change — a point in time that was critical for the development of wind energy in North Holland — i.e (1) the 2013 Energy Agreement, (2) the 2019 Climate Agreement, (3) the 2022 energy crisis. The historical narrative is followed by an 'Analysis and Discussion' section (Section 5) along with the following analytical questions:

- which **governance arrangements and processes** are in place; that is, what was the ensemble of actors (human and non-human) that come together in the intentional coordination of social action around wind energy (for and against wind energy);
- which **regulatory, normative and cultural-cognitive institutions** are co-shaping social activities around wind energy (these can derive from EU, national, regional and local, for instance, planning processes and landscape governance);
- which **participatory practices** are being discussed and/or practised (or not) over time and how are they being perceived and implemented by diverse wind actors;
- and how are notions of **energy justice and energy sovereignty** being discussed, narrated, and practised (or not) over time? How do they relate to changing governance arrangements and processes?

2 KEY INSIGHTS

Wind on land: from business opportunity to citizen engagement

In the evolution of onshore wind energy in North Holland, the shift from purely business opportunities to active citizen engagement has been pivotal. Initially, wind development was primarily an **economic pursuit**, with private companies capitalising on the renewable sector's profitability. However, as projects expanded, citizens became increasingly involved, particularly through Renewable Energy Strategies (RES), which facilitated local stakeholder input in energy projects. This participatory approach was not without challenges; opposition to onshore wind projects often arose from concerns over environmental impact, property values, and aesthetic disruptions. Nevertheless, such resistance became a driving force for integrating citizens into the heart of wind energy planning and governance. This process ensured that their voices were not only heard but also acted upon, making **community engagement** a critical element of sustainable wind energy development. Through collaborative efforts, citizens transitioned from passive observers to active participants and co-creators in the wind energy narrative, embodying the transition toward a more inclusive and sustainable energy future. Nevertheless, ongoing resistance to onshore wind has placed the majority of focus on offshore development in the coming years.

Future: acceleration of wind energy

Our research shows that wind energy is increasingly seen as the outcome of many societal issues. Whereas in its early years of development, it was mainly seen as a way to mitigate climate change, this has now expanded to providing an alternative to the earthquakes in Groningen caused by gas extraction, and a solution towards energy independence from geopolitically wrought Russian gas. This, combined with the fact that wind energy has become more affordable over the years, has led to the ambition to scale up wind energy from 10 GW in 2023, towards at least 70 GW in 2050.

Risks of accelerating wind: wind energy as a silver bullet

The risk of such an acceleration phase in societal transitions is that we **lose sight of the bigger picture**. Rather than seeing wind energy as a means to an end, installing wind becomes the goal itself. In an effort to tackle complex societal challenges as fast and efficiently as possible, we forget that transitions are deeply political and complex, and choose to see technological substitution as a silver bullet.

Recommendation: scale-up social innovation

Our research shows that the discourse around wind energy development has become increasingly **techno-optimist**, with varying efforts towards social innovation. While onshore wind energy has undergone large efforts towards citizen participation, just distribution of benefits and open and inclusive decision-making models, *offshore* wind lacks these efforts thus far. Our appraisal is that the proximity of energy towards citizens created contestation and protest. These protests have alerted governments (local, regional and national) to take citizen participation as a cornerstone of wind energy development. The case study shows that the **lack of proximity to wind development** has coincided with a **lack of citizen engagement towards wind energy** and a **depoliticisation** of wind energy. We recommend that the work that has been done on social innovation on land should not be foregone when scaling up wind at sea. The energy transition provides the **opportunity** to tackle unfair distributions of burdens and benefits: a chance to come up with innovative ownership models and scale up citizen-led decision-making. By merely understanding the transition as an exercise in technical scale-up, we miss the chance to institutionalise social innovation.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 DATA COLLECTION

JustWind4All takes a mixed-method approach to analyse historical developments and phases of wind energy governance within case study regions to formulate recommendations. The focus throughout the research is on the evolution of actor and governance arrangements, as well as participation and energy justice in relation to wind development over time. This case study on North Holland, the Netherlands, traces wind energy governance over the **focus period** of 2013-2023, with the addition of a **pre-period** for historical context. The focus period was subdivided into phases based on **critical instances of change (CICs)**, which are defined as points in time that were critical to the development of wind energy in North Holland.

A document review was conducted to inform the pre-period and focus period. In addition, a media analysis was performed to expand upon developments in the focus period. Furthermore, several interviews were conducted with relevant actors for wind energy development in North Holland to confirm and add to findings from the document and media reviews. The methodology for each of these three research methods is detailed below. In addition, two webinars related to the Dutch energy context were attended (see Annex 4).

3.1.1 DOCUMENT REVIEW

A document review of 50 documents including journal articles, reports, and policy documents was conducted. First, a systematic literature search was performed through the Web of Science and Scopus databases to obtain relevant journal articles. The results of the search and the exclusion criteria used are detailed in Figure 7. This literature search resulted in nine journal articles that qualified for the document review, indicating sparsity in the literature on the topic. In addition, six relevant policy documents and reports were selected from snowballing reference lists and additional internet searches. The list of documents reviewed can be found in Annex 1.

Media Analysis

The rest of the documents reviewed were in the form of local newspaper articles, selected through a media analysis. The goal of the media analysis was to collect primary sources which provide insight into local narratives, contestations, and happenings which are unlikely to make it into journal articles and reports. LexisNexis was used for media article searching. Two local newspapers were selected: Noordhollands Dagblad and Het Parool. Het Parool is an Amsterdam daily newspaper and generally adopts a politically left-leaning, Amsterdam-based lens in its reporting. Noordhollands Dagblad overall represents smaller municipalities in North Holland outside of the urban centre of Amsterdam and generally reports with a more conservative lens. Together, the two newspapers were selected to represent the province as a whole.

Search terms pertaining to wind energy in North Holland between 2013 and 2023 were used (NL: “windpark* or windenergie* or windmol*”). As the search yielded over 15,000 results, further refining was required. A timeline analysis was therefore performed to identify peak periods for wind-energy-related newspaper articles. Three periods were identified, and search results were refined to these periods. These included the spring of 2015, fall of 2020, and spring of 2021, mainly corresponding to provincial elections, the first RES report deadline and the opening of a large wind park, and further debate over RES plans, respectively. Then, newspaper article titles and texts were screened for

relevance to wind energy governance, participation, justice, or public acceptance in North Holland. From the results, approximately 35 articles were selected for inclusion in the document review.

Figure 7. Steps performed in systematic literature search for journal articles.

3.1.3 INTERVIEWS

In parallel to the document review, several interviews were conducted. Notable figures were collected from the newspaper articles analysed from the document review. In addition, key individuals in the CICs, namely, the formation of the RES regions (see section 4.4 for details), were identified and compiled. The goal was to interview a range of stakeholders, including civil servants, wind energy researchers or experts (both onshore and offshore), energy cooperative members, local residents, resistance groups, and journalists. A list of 20 potential interviewees was made with a relatively even distribution of the aforementioned actors. First, the top 10 potential interviewees were contacted via email and a follow-up email was sent in the absence of a reply. This was repeated until at least five interviews were planned. Potential interviewees were also identified through referrals from other interviewees.

In total, eight interviewees were interviewed between May and October 2023 (see Annex 2: Interviewees for details). Interviews were held in Dutch, and the interview guide, participant information and ethical review form were translated into Dutch. The interview guide was used by the researchers to conduct the interviews, which was adjusted to the knowledge area of each interviewee

accordingly. Interviews were semi-structured, allowing for follow-up questions and liberties on behalf of the interviewer. Interviews lasted between 60 and 90 minutes.

The interviews were recorded with consent from the interviewees and later transcribed using transcription software. Interviewees were sent the draft transcript and provided the opportunity to revise or redact any statements. Interviewees also selected whether they could be quoted and how they would be referred to in the report (role title, name, anonymous, etc) and asked if they had further information to share following the interview.

3.2 DATA ANALYSIS

Selected documents and transcripts were analysed through qualitative coding using the software Atlas.ti (2023). Deductive codes were defined and adjusted throughout the coding process. A list of codes used can be found in Annex 3. For the first 10 documents, a first and second reviewer was assigned in order to align code interpretation within the research team. After exchanging feedback, the remaining documents and transcripts were divided and coded by an individual researcher. Once all documents and transcripts were coded, codes were synthesised through a memo-writing process. These intermediate memos were used to inform the pre-period, focus period, analysis, synthesis and recommendations.

3.3 EMPIRICAL REFLECTIONS

This case study was conducted by a team of researchers in the Netherlands, consisting of two researchers/consultants, and one research assistant. Our relative proximity to the province of North Holland within the Netherlands allowed for ease of travel and on-site interviews, as well as a relative familiarity with the local energy system prior to beginning research on the case study. While two members of the research team were Dutch themselves, one member was not a native Dutch speaker. This required the frequent use of translation software for documents and may have resulted in a level of cross-cultural misinterpretation in understanding underlying connotations in interviews and documents alike. Nevertheless, our variation in cultural backgrounds allowed for a breadth of perspectives in approaching and interpreting the research.

One of the largest barriers we faced was in reaching a diverse and representative **range of interviewees**. Our interviewee **sampling** strategy focused on the balanced involvement of both pro-, neutral, and anti-wind voices, as well as a diverse set of actor roles. While we tried to follow these principles when reaching out to potential interviewees, we struggled with a lack of responsiveness or interest from both anti-wind voices and citizen groups and a disproportionate response from government actors. As our sampling technique later involved snowballing through referrals from past interviewees, this skewed sample grew as interviewees generally referred us to those with similar perspectives to themselves. In addition, we had difficulty in finding interviewees who had insights into Phase 1 (2013-2019), as most actors had only been involved in the Dutch wind energy scene since the creation of the RES regions. This further indicates the uptick in engagement that defines the Climate Agreement described in the Phase 2.

As a result, we relied heavily on media articles in our literature sampling to incorporate the voices lacking in our interviewees. Our document sampling strategy remained relatively systematic, although peer-reviewed texts were relatively limited, further leading towards the focus on media articles. In

addition, our team attended two webinars regarding citizen participation in the Dutch renewable energy context (see Annex 4). This provided for further interviewee contacts, new insights, and a sense check on the conclusions we had already drawn. Together, these three methods allowed us to **triangulate** findings through cross-checking and providing alternate perspectives.

As researchers, we attempted to retain a balance of proximity and distance in relation to the case study. While we were familiar with the dynamics of the Dutch energy landscape, we ensured that we had no prior relation to the interviewees. When contacting potential interviewees, we attempted to use neutral wording which avoided implying the need for wind energy “acceleration” or “future development” in order to reach a broad audience. However, we ran into the reputation of our organisation DRIFT as activist action researchers, which recipients often had preconceived notions regarding our interests and motivations. This likely contributed to our difficulty in reaching voices of opposition. When planning and shaping interviews, we aimed to be flexible, respect the time and attune to the personal interests of our interviewees. Further improvements could be made in involving interviewees with further JustWind4All activities, however, this may still come down the line.

In summary, our case study navigated various challenges, from cultural and linguistic barriers to sampling biases and preconceptions about our research team's affiliations. Despite these hurdles, we employed a multifaceted approach that combined on-site interviews, media analysis, and webinar participation to enrich our understanding of the Dutch wind energy landscape. The insights gained from this study not only contribute to our knowledge base but also highlight the complexities of engaging a wide range of stakeholders in discussions about renewable energy development. Moving forward, it will be crucial to develop strategies that mitigate the observed biases and engage underrepresented voices more effectively.

4 WIND ENERGY GOVERNANCE IN NORTH HOLLAND

This section presents the historical development of wind energy narratives and governance in North Holland, beginning in the 1970s up until 2023. First, the pre-period of 1970-2013 is briefly summarised, as to provide context for the in-depth focus period. The focus period consists of three main phases, which are each bookended by a CIC. A CIC in this case refers to a moment or period in time that changed the course of how wind energy has been governed in North Holland. These phases are:

1. 2013-2019: Governments take the lead
2. 2019-2021: National ambitions, local engagement
3. 2022-2023: Energy security and offshore ambitions

The corresponding CICs are:

1. The 2013 Energy Agreement
2. The 2019 Climate Agreement
3. The onset of the global energy crisis in 2022

The timeline in Figure 7 provides an overview of these developments, including influential developments in (inter)national policy, local policy, and participation. Before going into the phases and CICs, we describe the period leading up to this era: the pre-period (Section 5.1).

4.1 PRE-PERIOD

The history of modern wind energy technology in the Netherlands began in the 1970s, which marks the start of the pre-period. The pre-period is divided into three phases, distinguished by the oil crises in the 1970s, the liberalisation of the Dutch energy market in 1998, and the formative national and provincial elections in the early 2010s. Each phase is briefly presented below.

1973-1997: Seedlings of wind energy amidst an inflexible regime

There is a long history of wind energy in the Netherlands, but modern wind turbine development began following the 1970s energy crisis and the Chernobyl disaster in 1986 (Agterbosch & Breukers, 2008). Prior to the energy crisis, the Netherlands was entirely dependent on natural gas, however, the energy crisis drew greater attention towards alternative energy technologies, mainly nuclear energy, and the beginnings of renewable energy (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018). Once the risks of nuclear energy hit the public eye in the 80s, serious investigation into wind energy began. This was spurred on by environmental concerns as well as criticisms of economic growth stemming from the Club of Rome in 1975 (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018).

“The Dutch energy discourse changed after the oil crises. The oil crises had revealed a strong dependence on foreign imports of fossil fuels, causing the government to aspire a firmer grip on the energy system. Meanwhile, a public debate emerged on the undesirability of nuclear power and environmental concerns. The previously stable dominant discourse of economic growth and technological opportunities was challenged from many sides, including feminism, anarchism and radical environmentalism.” (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018, p. 56).

Not long after, the first citizen renewable energy communities were constructed in the form of local cooperatives in the late 80s in North Holland, which by then already had positioned itself as a leading province in wind energy (van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020a). In the 1990s, these communities erected a

small number of shared locally-owned wind turbines throughout the province, which centred around a “discourse that combined environmental concerns with a wish for local independence” (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018, p. 56). However, power in the energy market during this period was concentrated in a few select stakeholders – mainly regional companies with provinces and municipalities as shareholders: “The focus in the actor constellation was on the government and large market players such as the fossil fuel industry and energy intensive industry” (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018, p. 56). In other words, “The wind power market was not freely accessible” to those outside of the select market players, who were yet to turn their sights on renewables (Agterbosch & Breukens, 2008, p. 396).

In contrast to discourses held by wind energy cooperatives, the discourse of the regime during this period was unreceptive to wind energy. “In general, wind power was not perceived by distributors to be a technical and economically attractive investment with future potential. Moreover, they were inexperienced in the planning of decentralized facilities. The implementation trajectories of these decentralized large-scale wind power facilities were characterized by lead times of an average of more than 6 years.” (Agterbosch & Breukens, 2008, p. 396).

The above developments resulted in 323 turbines and 50 MW of installed capacity in the Netherlands by 1990, with 68 turbines and 10 MW of installed capacity in North Holland specifically. By the end of the phase in 1997, this number had grown to 1,148 and 324 MW, respectively (181 turbines and 39 MW in North Holland) (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2023). As for offshore wind, although a considered alternative for renewable energy since the 1970s, it was dismissed during this period as it was deemed too expensive (Kern et al., 2015).

1998-2009: Liberalisation and innovation

The early 2000s can be characterised by a severing in national and local opinion regarding wind energy: at a national level there was government support and a positive public opinion, but when plans became tangible near residents’ opposition arose. This suggests that policies did not match peoples’ willingness to accept the present approach to wind energy development (Agterbosch et al., 2009).

This began with the liberalisation of the Dutch energy market in 1998 with the Dutch Electricity and Gas Act, following the EU’s 1996 decision to open up energy markets for large companies (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018). The liberalisation of the consumer market followed in 2004. This changed the landscape of wind energy drastically, as wind energy became profitable for private producers. “The liberalisation of the market, a substantial improvement in the profitability of projects due to changes in financial incentive schemes and a large consumer demand added to the implementation capacity for private producers and these changing conditions have been crucial for their growing entrance.” (Agterbosch & Breukens, 2008, p. 396).

This resulted in several large-scale projects facilitated by energy companies cooperating with distributors. The subsidisation of renewable energy emerged with a series of subsidy schemes devised by the Dutch government. Notably, the Stimulation Regulation Sustainable Energy Production (SDE) subsidy scheme was created in 2008, to stimulate innovation in hopes of renewable energy development becoming subsidy-independent in the future (Fraaije et al., 2021). This scheme was the baseline for ensuing subsidies, the framework of which is still used today. As a result, onshore wind energy grew to an installed capacity of 1876 MW by the end of 2009, with 315 MW in North Holland (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek, 2023). However, the decentralised nature of renewable energy and its potential for greater involvement of local communities as compared to fossil fuels was new to developers. As put by Agterbosch & Breukens (2008), “Energy distributors were inexperienced in the

planning of decentralized facilities and often used a top-down planning approach ignoring public discussions on the local governmental level. These discussions concerned aspects such as landscape value, beliefs about interference such as noise hindrance, and financial benefits. Ignoring these local interests created conflicts at the community level. A clear national-local divide can be observed: local conflicts were at odds with socio-political acceptance (of renewables) and the corresponding public policy framework at the level of central and provincial authorities.” (p. 404).

As a result of this top-down approach and national-local divide, societal opposition grew towards onshore wind during this period. This led to renewed interest in offshore wind in the late 1990s and early 2000s (Kern et al., 2015). The national government determined that investment in offshore wind was feasible in 1999, which was followed by the construction of a tender system and a Renewable production stimulation scheme (MEP) available to both on- and offshore wind (Kern et al., 2015). After a series of planning negotiations and protests against the potential marine biodiversity impacts of offshore wind, the first offshore wind park opened in 2006 (Kern et al., 2015; Steins et al., 2021).

2010-2012: Navigating political currents

The early 2010s were characterized by a rapid shift in wind energy narratives and regulations, particularly in North Holland. National elections in 2010 and provincial elections in 2011, following the economic crisis, resulted in more conservative coalitions and the shrinkage of green party support. With financial concerns at the forefront of politics, the new national government responded by shifting the narrative against renewable energy and towards nuclear energy, depicting renewables as expensive and ineffective (Kooij et al., 2018a). Renewable energy continued to be stimulated at the national level, with the updated subsidy scheme SDE+ put into place in 2011, although this iteration shifted its focus further towards economic efficiency in funding (Fraaije et al., 2021).

In North Holland, the rising opposition towards onshore wind expressed in the 2000s was matched with a proposed provincial halt on the issuing of new wind turbine permits by the new provincial government (“Noord Holland Wil Geen Windmolens Meer,” 2012). At this point, there were approximately 300 wind turbines in North Holland. While the halt on permits was later vetoed by the national government, the province regardless put forth stricter spatial regulations regarding turbines’ proximity to homes, increasing the national standard of 400 meters to a province-wide 600 meters. In addition, a new policy was established that stated that older turbines ready for decommissioning could only be placed one new turbine for every two older ones. Due to the high population density in North Holland, locations with a 600-meter radius that is clear of residences are highly uncommon. Thus, these provincial-wide restrictions nearly had the same effect in practice as the vetoed ban on wind turbines (van Zoelen, 2019).

Meanwhile, 2010 also marked the greenlighting of the wind park Wieringermeer, the largest onshore wind park in the Netherlands, in the north of North Holland. As the national government has jurisdiction over wind projects larger than 100 MW, the decision overruled any provincial decision-making (IEA, 2020b; “Tijdlijn,” 2020). This marked the start of a contentious decade which, for many residents in the area, sealed the lid on their opposition towards onshore wind (see section Participatory Practice 1 for detail). While this period is distinct in its political turnover compared to the previous pre-periods, the boundary between these years and the demarcation of the focus period (2013) is fuzzy. Large changes occurred at the national level, however, at the provincial level the events in 2010-2012 set the tone for 2013 up until 2019. This should be taken into account when reflecting upon the following phase.

4.2 TIMELINE

Classification: Internal

Figure 8. Timeline of wind energy development within the province of North Holland between the years of 2013-2023.

4.3 PHASE 1: GOVERNMENTS TAKE THE LEAD (2013-2019)

Context and critical instance:

- This phase is instigated by the launch of the national Energy Agreement (NL: Energieakkoord).
- The Energy Agreement is a critical instance of change (CIC) regarding wind development, as it: 1) set **provincial targets** for onshore wind development, and 2) restructured the offshore wind tendering process towards more **centralised national government** involvement.

Energy Agreement goals and targets

The Energy Agreement aimed for 14% of the national electricity mix to originate from renewable sources by the end of 2020 (Koelman et al., 2022). To achieve this goal, each province was prescribed a renewable energy target proportional to their perceived potential. North Holland received one of the highest targets of 685.5 MW of installed onshore renewable energy capacity, given its strong history in wind development (Interviewee 3; van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020b). The Energy Agreement defined a new phase in wind energy development as it was the first concrete national step towards a systematic, wide-scale renewable energy transition. While wind energy development was already underway in North Holland, many other provinces only began development following the agreement.

Shifting wind energy actor constellations

In terms of actor arrangements, the Energy Agreement made two main changes in the development process for onshore wind. Firstly, the demarcation of Energy Agreement wind plans at the provincial level placed provincial governments as the stewards of onshore renewable energy plans. This meant decision-making occurred at the provincial levels, providing flexibility for each province to shape its region-specific approach (Interviewee 3). On the other hand, the Energy Agreement introduced the Postcode Catchment Area scheme (NL: Postcoderoosregeling), which allowed residents whose postcode was within the surroundings of an energy cooperative to be exempted from paying energy taxes (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018; Verkade & Höffken, 2019). This marked the first legislation encouraging community energy groups, and led to an expansion in such initiatives, with 38 solar and wind postcode catchment projects realised in the Netherlands by 2016 (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018). Focus on development shifted towards the province, as well as local energy cooperatives, in contrast to the previous focus on private wind developers, as can be seen in Figure 10. However, the planning process still depended on private developers, or in some cases energy cooperatives, to initiate projects.

Tensions between local, regional and national authorities

The Energy Agreement demarcates the solidification of the rift between national policy, provincial interests, and local plans in North Holland. The newly mandated 685.5 MW directly opposed North Holland's plan to curb wind energy development (see also pre-period, Section 4.1) (Van Zoelen, 2019). In response to the goals, the province adopted a reluctant approach (Interviewee 4), approving enough plans to reach the target and no more, which in the end resulted in an undershoot of the 685.5 MW goal (van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020a; van Zoelen, 2019). As described by Van Aalderen & Horlings (2020), the provincial government of North Holland approached this period with "authoritative reluctance", with a particular disinterest in local efforts or citizen initiatives (p. 9). This created increasing tensions between the national and the provincial government. Moreover, it increased an ongoing divide between urban and rural positionings on wind development. Most opposition which fuelled the province's stance on wind energy development largely stemmed from rural areas. In contrast, urban centres, and in particular, the municipality of Amsterdam, held more progressive values. Several citizen initiatives attempted to initiate new wind projects, and the city council's stance was pro-wind development within Amsterdam. However, efforts were hampered by the province, with an estimated 50 proposed turbines turned down by the province during these years, resulting in

a lull in wind energy development during this period (van Zoelen, 2019). This resulted in frustration regarding the uniform governance applied to the province, which urban residents felt prioritised rural agendas (van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020a). One exception to this was Windmolen Boekel, a locally owned turbine constructed on a business park near Alkmaar. The wind turbine was a collaboration between local community renewable energy groups and the local municipalities. The parties jointly constructed ‘Stichting Administratiekantoor Windmolen Boekel’, through which residents own 37% of the wind turbine. While a remarkable project, it was the only of its kind during this phase.

Anti-wind opposition

In the meantime, anti-wind opposition rose throughout the country. This was especially true for rural areas in North Holland such as West Friesland and Wieringermeer, where the Wieringermeer wind park, the largest onshore wind park in the Netherlands to date, was in its planning phase. This anti-wind sentiment led to several anti-wind protests: one near Wieringermeer in 2013, one at the provincial house in Haarlem in 2015 by residents of West Friesland (a district within North Holland), and a large protest in Urk, within the province of Flevoland, in 2015, with a record-breaking number of 400 protesters (“Tijdljn,” 2020). For further detail on resistance towards the Wieringermeer wind park, see section Participatory Practice 1.

Participatory Practice 1: Prinses Ariane “Wieringermeer” Wind Park

The Prinses Ariane Wind Park, also known as the Wieringermeer Wind Park, is a notable example of a wind energy project in the province of North Holland, the Netherlands, where participatory practices have been employed. This case study highlights the engagement of local residents and the various factors that have shaped their participation.

In 2010, the Dutch government granted the tender to the large Swedish energy company Vattenfall to construct a 99-turbine onshore wind farm, the largest to date in the country, in the north-east corner of North Holland (“Tijdljn,” 2020). Whereas typically the province would have the decision-making power for wind farms, very large-scale wind farms fall under the jurisdiction of the national government. This alone began the top-down approach of the wind park, which immediately caught the attention of local residents. Local opposition was observed to start in 2013, when the first protest occurred. Opposition grew as time progressed, and in 2014 local residents organised the foundation Local Residents of the Wieringermeer Wind Turbines (NL: Omwonenden Windturbines Wieringermeer) because they felt their concerns were underrepresented by the local council (“Tijdljn,” 2020). The wind park developers attempted to offset negative effects on nearby landowners, which mainly consist of farmers, through a compensation scheme. A sliding scale, one-off payment was given dependent on the landowner’s proximity to the wind park site, with a maximum payment of approximately 2,500 euros. However, this effort was perceived as insufficient by the local population, especially by those further away from the site yet still in sight of the wind turbines.

To intensify the situation, local municipalities granted permits for the construction of new Microsoft data centres near the wind farm in 2015. This marked a turning point for public opposition, which previously was mainly centred around concerns over horizon pollution and emphasised the need for compensation. Once news of the data centres broke, public attitudes changed drastically, and questions of justice came to the centre of the debate (Ekker, 2020). While residents had previously been dissatisfied but somewhat reassured by the promise of local green energy as the ultimate outcome, the introduction of the data centres, which would use a significant portion of the energy to be generated, broke this promise (Interviewees 1 and 5). While the connection between the two projects is debated, the belief that the municipality was more interested in profits than the residents’ wellbeing and upholding promises remained. The local group ‘Red the Wieringermeer’ (Save the Wieringermeer), which is active to this day, has led a number of protests in response to the data centres (*Toekomst Wieringermeer*, n.d.). The result of these developments is a sentiment that has been made clear to politicians by local residents: “No new windmills in the tip of North

Holland... We look at it [Wieringermeer] and we don't receive the energy. We don't get the money. We do suffer." (Interviewee 5).

Before the park's opening in September 2020, developers proposed that one wind turbine within Wieringermeer wind park which would be owned by local shareholders. Nevertheless, the local council blocked the plan as it did not find sufficient shareholders in time (Deutekom, 2019a). However, certain local groups still pushed for the initiative to be approved (Deutekom, 2019b). In addition, Vattenfall attempted to compensate local residents by dividing approximately €430,000 over 330 nearby addresses, with the potential to have a higher payout in high wind conditions (Soeters, 2020). In addition, part of the profits, €750,000, from the project are used for the construction of a 'Windfund', which invited local initiatives to apply for funding on a yearly basis. This is an attempt to work towards distributive justice, where the benefits from the wind farm are given back to the community (Ooms, 2023). However, even after the wind park has been in full operation, protests have not subsided. In 2021, local residents attempted to start a legal battle against the municipality for the wind farm permits, as some turbines were in a different spot than originally planned. However, this was shut down by the municipality, stating that the difference was too minimal to change the integrity of the project.

In conclusion, the participatory practices were shaped by regulatory, normative, and cultural-cognitive institutions and broader system developments. The national government's decision to grant the tender to Vattenfall set the stage for a top-down approach to the project. The introduction of the Microsoft data centres shifted the narrative of the wind farm and sparked further opposition. The local council's decision to block a proposed wind turbine owned by local shareholders also influenced the dynamics of participation. Issues of energy justice were central to the participatory practices, stemming from the construction of data centres which were perceived as diverting the clean energy promised to the local community. Residents felt that the benefits of the wind farm were not being equitably distributed, particularly with the introduction of the data centres. Vattenfall's compensation scheme and Windfund were attempts to address these concerns. However, protests and legal challenges have continued, indicating ongoing dissatisfaction with the project. As of March 2023, several members of Save the Wieringermeer are still trying to get their voices heard. While one public consultation with the Provincial Council occurred in 2021, residents feel that there has been an insufficient response from this consultation, and "they really need to consult with us again at some point" (van den Bos & Gutker, 2023)

Overall, participatory practices surrounding the Prinses Ariane Wind Park highlight the complexities of wind energy governance. While there were efforts to involve the public and distribute benefits equitably, these were met with significant opposition and controversy. This case displays changing perceptions and priorities over time, and underscores the importance of meaningful participation, fair benefit distribution, and transparent communication in achieving just and effective wind energy governance.

A more proactive national government in offshore wind development

While offshore wind had previously been regarded as too expensive, substantial technological advances rendered offshore wind an increasingly attractive alternative to onshore wind, which had been leading to protests and contestations. Therefore, the national government opted for increased offshore development, a substantial portion of which was to be installed off the coast of North Holland.

To meet heightened offshore wind targets, the national government reorganised the tendering procedure to have greater governmental influence on the speed of wind development. In doing so, the responsibility for offshore development shifted to the national government, rather than private wind developers. The Energy Agreement was a key change-maker that shifted these responsibilities. In the 2022 Dutch Offshore Wind manual, a reflection upon the influence of the Energy Agreement states "Looking back at the successful Roadmap 2023, it is safe to conclude that the Energy Agreement

proved to be a ‘game changer’ for the development of offshore wind in the Netherlands.” (wind & water works et al., 2022).

Figure 9 provides an overview of the change in the offshore wind actor constellation stemming from the Energy Agreement. Before 2013, private wind developers were responsible for the initiation and facilitation of the entirety of the tendering process, from site selection to performing an environmental impact assessment, to coordinating with grid operators to connect the wind park to the grid, while the role of the government was strictly to subsidise projects to make them economically interesting to investors. This is because of high start-up costs for project developers and a high market price for offshore wind, government subsidies were required for the investment to be profitable. This setup was incompatible with the increasingly ambitious national government goals. While it allowed for the establishment of the first wind parks in the Netherlands in the early 2000s (with a total installed capacity of 1 GW), it was considered too inefficient to result in the goal of 4.5 GW installed capacity in offshore wind by 2023 (wind & water works et al., 2022). Under the old model, alignment between offshore wind targets and wind developers was difficult, and the speed of development was dependent on individual developer interests, which could not guarantee reaching policy targets. In addition, the lack of standardisation in environmental impact assessments and site selection raised concerns over the effects on marine health.

A legal framework which defined clear jurisdiction over offshore wind planning was installed alongside the Energy Agreement, representing a more proactive national policy approach (wind & water works et al., 2022). This gave the national government jurisdiction over the tendering process, including site selection, impact assessments, and wind park specifications. Under the new system, which still stands today, the Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate (EZK), the Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO), and the national grid operator TenneT work together to design a tender for an offshore wind park. The role of developers is minimised, in that the government announces the tender (which is an all-inclusive package of wind farm, permit and installation) and allows developers to bid on it, with some room for negotiation of project specifications. In addition, a public consultation is mandated for each proposed tender, with the option for citizens to appeal – providing a demarcated role for public involvement. This setup, which is still in place in 2023, allows for standardisation in offshore wind park specification, and greater control of offshore wind development targets on behalf of the Dutch government (*Dutch Offshore Wind Guide, 2022*).

Currently, the Netherlands is on track for 4.7 GW of installed capacity of offshore wind in the Dutch North Sea by the end of 2023, with several offshore wind parks off the coast of North Holland (*The Netherlands on Track with Approach to Offshore Wind Energy, 2023*). In addition, since 2013, the cost of offshore wind has dropped by 80%, and necessary government subsidies have decreased by two-thirds (wind & water works et al., 2022).

Summary:

- The 2013 Energy Agreement in the Netherlands served as a pivotal turning point in the development of wind energy.
- For both on- and offshore wind, it shifted the focus from private developers to the influence of governing bodies, setting concrete national goals for renewable energy.
- For onshore wind projects, it also introduced innovative policies to encourage community involvement.
- While it led to resistance and tension, especially in onshore wind development, it spurred significant growth in offshore wind projects, marked by greater government control and collaboration.

Figure 9. The planning process for the development of an offshore wind park in the Netherlands, before the 2013 Energy Agreement, and after the 2013 Energy Agreement. Government actors are marked in green, market actors are marked in blue, and public actors are marked in grey. Based on (Dutch Offshore Wind Guide, 2022).

4.4 PHASE 2: NATIONAL AMBITIONS, LOCAL ENGAGEMENT (2019-2021)

Context and critical instance:

- **Climate Agreement (2019):** After nearly a decade of a provincial stalemate in wind energy development, the introduction of a new national climate agreement in 2019 resulted in a major shift in wind energy governance. The Climate Agreement (NL: Klimaatakkoord), an overarching climate policy that replaced the 2013 Energy Agreement, redefined the Dutch climate ambitions: halving carbon emissions by 2030 and developing 35 TWh of onshore solar and wind by 2035.
- **Regional Energy Strategies:** While this marked a large uptick in ambitions, the significant shift that the Climate Agreement instituted was the formation of the Regional Energy Strategies (RES). While previously onshore wind energy governance took place at the provincial level, the RES introduced a new level of governance – 30 RES regions across the country, each of which was responsible for setting targets and plans in a bottom-up manner that focused on participation and a fair distribution of impacts. The RES constitute a CIC as it restructured actor roles in wind energy governance, and vastly altered how projects were planned.
- **Anti-wind protests:** This period brought renewable energy (including wind energy) into the public eye, bringing out both pro- and anti-wind sentiment and placing them head-to-head, on- as well as offshore.

Formation of RES regions and search areas

The Climate Agreement in part came about due to the mandated EU National Energy and Climate Plans (NECP), in which each member state was required to devise a NECP with binding climate targets to be approved by the EU (IEA, 2022). Within the agreement, updated renewable energy targets were set with the goal of 70% of electricity generated by renewable energy by 2030 (*Elektriciteit*, 2019). However, the most influential aspect of the Climate Agreement for onshore wind energy development was the designation and formation of the Renewable Energy Strategy (RES) regions. After the Netherlands failed to achieve Energy Agreement targets for renewable energy, the government decided a new and innovative approach must be taken which allowed for greater participation, in hopes of mediating citizen resistance (*Nationaal Programma Regionale Energiestrategie*, n.d.). The RES divided the country into 30 regions of wind and solar development, which together must collaborate to reach a national goal of 35 TWh of onshore renewable energy generation by 2030 (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). By 2020, the newly introduced RES regions constituted a new level of governance for wind energy that bridged the local municipal level and the provincial level.

The result was a new governance constellation and approach to wind energy planning. As shown in Figure 10, before 2019 mid-scale (5-100 MW) wind parks were designed and initiated largely by private developers and then approved or denied by the province. Along with the designation of the RES regions came a new method of wind park development: search areas (NL: zoekgebieden). Rather than wind park locations chosen by developers and later discussed with local inhabitants, search areas are locations for future wind and solar development, designated and agreed upon by local stakeholders (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021; Interviewee 4). These areas could then be offered to developers, after which local negotiation would in theory be minimised. Restricting renewable energy development to areas determined to suit local interests aimed to mediate local resistance which had stalled onshore renewable energy development in the Netherlands. This shift is reminiscent of the 2013 restructuring of offshore wind tendering in the Energy Agreement (see Figure 8), as the location and specification of wind parks were shifted from developer-driven to government-initiated.

RES targets and timeline

The RES regions intended to be bottom-up in decision-making processes. While a national target of 35 TWh onshore renewable electricity by 2030 was set, the Climate Agreement did not designate regional targets. Each RES region was responsible for internally agreeing on their relative contribution to this goal. Currently, the 30 regions' goal adds up to 41 TWh. Aside from this, each region has certain requirements between 2020 and 2030 (Monster, 2022):

- *October 2020*: Submit a draft of the first regional RES report, focused on the regional approach but also including draft search areas and targets.
- *July 2021*: Submit RES 1.0, the officialised version of the draft RES report with confirmed search areas.
- *July 2023*: Progress report.
- *2022-2024*: RES recalibration 2.0 report. Submission of adjustment to targets, search areas, and plans.
- *January 2025*: All permits for achieving the 2030 target must be submitted.
- *July 2025*: Progress report.
- *January 2030*: Deadline for goal of 35 TWh onshore renewable electricity.

In North Holland specifically, the province was split into two RES regions: North Holland North, which predominantly consists of rural municipalities, and North Holland South, which captures the urban centres of Amsterdam and Haarlem. While targets and search areas differed between the regions, their approach was the same, as exemplified by the identical text in their RES 1.0 reports (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021, 2021b). In addition, those coordinating the two RES regions worked together closely at the province, which resulted in a relatively small split between the province and the RES regions, in comparison to some other provinces where RES regions worked independently from one another (Interviewee 4). In the case of North Holland, RES employees were connected to the province and were in frequent communication. In terms of differences between the regions (see Table 2), both regions were ambitious in their targets, although wind energy made up a small share of plans in both regions relative to solar. This is likely a result of ongoing local pushback to wind energy in comparison to solar when designating search areas, as well as the influence of the recently opened Wieringermeer wind park in the northern region, which utilised a large portion of land with onshore wind potential (Interviewee 1).

Table 2. RES 1.0 report targets and plans from RES regions in the province of North Holland (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). *See Participatory Practice 2 for details).

	2030 TARGET (TWH)	TARGET INCREASE FROM STATUS QUO 2021-2030 (TWH)	SHARE OF WIND ENERGY IN PLANS (% TWH)
NORTH HOLLAND NORTH	3.6 (+1.1*)	1.5 (+1.1*)	8.2
NORTH HOLLAND SOUTH	2.7	2.0	11.8

Approach and guiding principles

As for the approach taken by the two regions, an extensive formulation process was undertaken which attempted to include a range of stakeholders. Overall, the province of North Holland was notable for its intensive focus on participation relative to other regions (Interviewee 4). The 2020 draft RES reports were a product of discussions with grid operators, local residents, entrepreneurs, energy cooperatives, housing corporations, the agricultural sector, youths, and social organisations related to nature and the environment (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). First, each RES region was divided into sub-regions which each drafted three scenarios for the region. These scenarios were scrutinised through a number of avenues, including reflection sessions and discussion bus tours which engage with local residents and stakeholders; 12 sessions with renewable energy experts and civil servants; discussions with 50 young people across five secondary schools, and 44 local meetings where over 1500 local residents attended. From this, a draft RES was published in April 2020. This was followed by further avenues of participation, with the following six months dedicated to compiling 245 pieces of feedback from governing bodies as well as 120 reactions from local residents and stakeholders. This was followed by a subsequent round of knowledge and inspiration sessions, eight focus group meetings, and 55 local meetings and studies to form the RES 1.0 report which was published in July 2021 (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). Quotes from residents' feedback and proposed alterations to search areas or overall approach were integrated into the report, such as the quote from a youth discussion emphasising how the process should focus on working "creatively towards a new normal" (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021, p. 24). The result from this process, aside from designated search areas, was the delineation of eight guiding principles of the RES region's approach (NL: uitgangspunten). Throughout the RES process, an estimated 3,500 residents were consulted (Interviewee 4).

Guiding Principles RES North Holland

The RES process has brought a lot of people to the table. Meetings have been organised in the sub-regions and municipalities, knowledge has been shared and discussions were held.

In the process, the following guiding principles for the follow-up steps were formulated:

1. *Careful participation*: residents and other stakeholders can contribute their ideas and municipalities facilitate resident initiatives.
2. *Fair distribution of benefits and burdens*: always aim for a minimum of 50% local ownership per project.
3. Each project will aim to *add value for landscape and nature* and measures will be taken to prevent or reduce negative impacts on local communities and ecosystems.
4. Each project will *explore how opportunities can be linked*, or where *generation can be combined* with other functions.
5. The *legal frameworks for distance and (noise) nuisance* remain the starting point. Local authorities can decide on stricter standards.
6. *Quickly realisable* projects such as solar on large roofs, car parks and noise barriers are actively encouraged.
7. There is and will continue to be *room for new initiatives and search areas*.
8. *Spatial cohesion* is important. The province takes the lead to monitoring.

Source: RES 1.0 Noord-Holland North/South: <https://energieregionhz.nl/app/uploads/2021/04/nhz-samenvatting.pdf>

The first point to come out of the discussions in both regions was the need for participation from start (2019) to finish (2030) (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). This demonstrated a willingness from stakeholders to participate, matched with openness from the RES governing body, which describes their overall approach as 'bottom-up' in the plans. In addition, distribution justice, phrased as "fair distribution of benefits and burdens" is ranked highly in importance, and executed through

the requirement of 50% local ownership for each renewable energy project. These foci demonstrate how the Climate Agreement went beyond the Energy Agreement in terms of participatory and just practices, as citizens were included in many steps of the planning process, and the term ‘justice’ is explicitly used for the first time. In addition to distributive justice, intergenerational justice was also considered, acknowledging that future generations are the most impacted by climate adaptation and mitigation, and yet are often lacking representation (Duckworth, 2013). Therefore, high school students were included in round table discussions on RES plans, and an empty chair representing future generations was placed at RES meetings (Interviewee 2).

Participatory Practice 2: Alternative Regional Energy Strategies proposals in North Holland

As described in Section 4.4, the RES 1.0 report was published in 2021. In drafting this report, consisting of search areas for future renewable energy development, citizen involvement was invited, and feedback incorporated in subsequent drafts. Over 150 citizen remarks and alternative proposals were submitted based on the first RES draft in 2020 for both North Holland North and South.

Notably, two alternative RES plans were submitted. Firstly, Kor Buitendijk, a local resident of Wieringermeerhoek, submitted a proposal for ‘nature islands’ off the coast of the north-east corner of North Holland, which would consist of man-made islands covered in a combination of solar panels, wind turbines and native plants. With an estimated energy generation potential of 1.1 TWh, and its synergy with local biodiversity goals of the local area, the plan was well received and gained significant local news coverage. The RES region welcomed the plan and incorporated it into the RES 1.0, which was published in July 2021 (Buitendijk, 2021). The feasibility and logistics of the plan is now being investigated by consultants and contractors.

Secondly, public debate occurred regarding the overall approach of the RES plans. Some felt that the syphoning of renewable energy plans into strict search areas was too restrictive and prescriptive. As a result, two organisations - Economisch Forum Noord Holland boven Amsterdam (Economic Forum North Holland above Amsterdam) and Natuur en Milieu Federatie Noord-Holland (Nature and Environmental Federation North Holland) - joined forces to submit an alternative approach to the RES plans in North Holland North entitled “Van Kaart naar Vaart” (*Economie Stimuleren En Natuur Respecteren*, 2020). The letter states that there is too little room to “colour outside the lines” in current plans, and suggests changes to the approach, mainly: ongoing flexibility for amendments and the development of new search areas, emphasises the need for local financial ownership of projects and the protection of nature and landscapes, expand participation opportunities for businesses, place greater focus on energy saving or sufficiency alongside upscaling renewable energy, and allow room for innovation and other renewable energy types (Economisch Forum Holland boven Amsterdam & natuur en milieu federatie noord-holland, 2020). Despite this form of participation being uninvited, the director of the Nature and Environmental Federation North Holland emphasised that the letter was received well by RES planners (Interviewee 5). However, the administrative structure (pillarization) of government created a roadblock to effective implementation of the suggestions. According to the director, the RES board were limited in the degree to which they could take up the suggestions (in spite of their wishes to do so) as policy areas are clearly divided, meaning by suggesting a broader more innovative approach cross-policy area implementation was not possible (Interviewee 5). While the suggestions were implemented in their respective policy areas, the lack of interdisciplinary policy reduced the power of the original package of amendments as a whole.

Challenges and uncertainties

It is difficult to determine the effectiveness of these principles in further decision-making. The legal encoding of these principles depends on the implementation of a new Environmental Act (NL: Omgevingswet) and Energy Act (NL: Energiewet), both of which have been delayed for a number of years (“Invoering Omgevingswet Weer Uitgesteld, Naar Januari Volgend Jaar,” 2023; Wijzigingswet Elektriciteitswet 1998, enz. (voortgang energietransitie), 2021; Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). Until these are implemented, the RES is not able to work effectively towards its intended goals of justice and participation.

To date, principles are not legally binding, which places the responsibility on municipalities to enforce adherence within their jurisdiction. This is particularly pertinent to the requirement of 50% local ownership, which is often interpreted differently by parties and not strongly enforced by governing bodies, limiting its effectiveness (Interviewees 1 and 5). Ensuring participation is also the responsibility of municipalities in combination with project developers (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021). This reflects the shift in responsibility in wind energy development from project developers in coordination with the province towards the municipal level with the Climate Agreement. This shift, in combination with the growing involvement of local interest groups such as residents or organisations, has created a lack of clarity in responsibilities, and left municipalities struggling to catch up (Interviewee 1). This was particularly difficult for small municipalities that have a limited budget for staff specialised in sustainability or energy. The focus on role changes in this period also led to a large uptick in discussion around renewable energy. However, embodying new roles and defining search areas meant wind project implementation was generally absent during this period.

Influence of external factors

In addition to the Climate Agreement, coinciding events contributed to wind energy development in 2019-2021. Firstly, provincial elections in 2019 revealed increasing support for the green party, which re-entered into the North Holland coalition after being absent for over a decade (Slot & Hylkema, 2019). This indicated a shift in public opinion towards issues of sustainability and allowed for increased interest in renewable energy in comparison to the approach in the previous decade. In addition, a series of earthquakes occurred in the province of Groningen due to the extraction of natural gas, which resulted in pressure on the Dutch government to search for alternative energy sources. This likely contributed to the heightened ambitions in the Climate Agreement and public openness towards alternative energy technologies (IEA, 2020).

Increasing protests against onshore wind: Windalarm

On the other hand, the citizen protest group Wind Alarm (NL: Windalarm), which is organised against the development of wind turbines in the urban environment, was created in 2020. What began as protests by local residents to a proposed wind farm near IJburg (part of the municipality of Amsterdam) grew into an organisation led by highly educated individuals who express health concerns, 'horizon pollution', and a number of other trade-offs associated with wind turbines (Interviewee 3). While not fundamentally opposed to wind energy, the group poses alternatives such as solely implementing offshore wind, energy reductions in industrial parks, solar roofs on every suitable building, and others to offset the need for onshore wind. The group runs courses on how to stall wind development and has had a strong influence in pushing back against the RES plans in North Holland. One interviewee estimated that the group alone was responsible for a year of setbacks in RES-related wind development in the municipality of Amsterdam (Interviewee 5). As a result of the group's actions, there is a reluctance reported on behalf of some policymakers in North Holland South to initiate wind projects as they do not wish to confront Wind Alarm (Koops & Van Zoelen, 2021).

Increasing protests against onshore wind: Wieringermeer

On the other side of the province, in the Wieringermeerhoek, another contestation brewed. The construction and opening of the Wieringermeer Wind Park, the largest Dutch wind park, concluded in September 2020. Due to its size (exceeding 100 MW), the wind park was commissioned under the jurisdiction of the national government rather than the province. Strong pushback occurred from local residents, who felt local interests were not prioritised. While promised a local distribution of benefits early in the planning process, residents felt this promise was broken later in the planning process due to the construction of nearby data centres near the wind park, which were perceived to divert benefits from local residents (see Participatory Practice 1 for more detail). Overall, contestation around

Wieringermeer and the concretisation of search areas played a large role in shaping this phase, as the uptick in resistance indicates a distinction from the relative silence that characterises the previous phase. While 2019-2021 spurred an expansion in wind energy discussion and plans, the restructuring of onshore wind energy actor roles that occurred in this phase meant few projects were implemented. Rather, many wind energy projects were placed in the pipeline for a later phase of widespread implementation.

A new frontier: offshore wind

In the period between 2015-2020, wind energy became increasingly pushed to (far) offshore areas, to meet climate demands whilst mitigating opposition against new developments by residents. This was made possible by the cost-reducing investments the national government had made regarding (far) offshore wind since the 1990s. However, this push did not resolve wind development contestation altogether. The North Sea is small and often cited to be the most intensively used sea in the world. As such, the push to offshore wind created a competition for sea-space between various interests, such as ecological NGOs, fishery representatives, and the marine and gas/oil industry. To overcome these frictions whilst meeting (inter)national climate goals and pushing offshore wind forward, the national government instated the North Sea Coalition (NL: Noordzeeoverleg) in 2019. This consultative body was created to find consensus amongst stakeholders about the future of wind development in the North Sea (Douvere, 2008; Overlegorgaan Fysieke Leefomgeving, 2020; Spijkerboer et al., 2020; Stelzenmüller et al., 2016; Wever et al., 2015). As quoted from its website: *“The Minister of Infrastructure and Water Management, also on behalf of the Ministers of Economic Affairs and Climate, Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality and the Interior, has asked the Consultative Body for the Physical Environment (OFL) to set up and implement a North Sea consultation together with the central government and stakeholders. to operate. The aim is to reach a 'North Sea Agreement' together with the relevant ministries and social parties.”* (Noordzeeoverleg, n.d.). There are 15 seats available, divided amongst five parties/sectors: seafaring, energy, nature, food and fishery and the national government. The North Sea coalition has a scientific council and a transition fund of 200 million euros, which it can spend on its innovation programme (Monitoring and Research Nature Enhancement and Species Protection, NL: MONS). In 2020, the coalition came to a North Sea Agreement. The agreement lists agreements between stakeholders about the development of wind energy until 2030 and the longer term. This includes site-selection aspects, informed the Maps of Wind at Sea (NL: Routekaarten Wind op Zee) and would become an important input to the national Programme North Sea that listed the plans for the North Sea from 2022-2027 (see Phase 2).

Offshore contestations: wind vs. fishery

Even though the North Sea Coalition aims to solve frictions around wind developments, not all conflicts proved to be easily resolvable. Frictions arose within the discussions around wind energy and 1) the future of the fishery sector and 2) the long-term impact on wildlife, nature, and ecology. In September 2020, these frictions led to two of the nine fishery delegates represented in the North Sea Coalition' refusal to sign the North Sea Agreement, stating in a heated letter to the Minister of Infrastructure, that *“the intentions in the North Sea Agreement regarding energy extraction in the North Sea [...] seriously threaten the prospects of the entire fishing chain”* (Overlegorgaan Fysieke Leefomgeving, 2020). As a consensus must exist among delegates for the sector to sign onto the Agreement, the fishery sector remains unrepresented in the Agreement as of 2023, and consensus is still being sought (Overlegorgaan Fysieke Leefomgeving, 2020).

The friction between wind and fishery demonstrates that wind development in the Netherlands challenges deep-rooted identities, values, and cultural histories. The dense population on land and

limited sea-space make these tensions even more fraught, resulting in local opposition and protest, from individual residents (onshore) as well as professional stakeholders (offshore).

Offshore contestations: wind vs. ecology

Alongside frictions with the fishery industry, the push to offshore wind led to concerns from ecologists and nature-oriented NGOs, such as Greenpeace and the North Sea Foundation (NL: Stichting De Noordzee). Their main concern is for a blind push for offshore wind, while the cumulative long-term effects of wind farms are still unknown (Interviewee 6). While there is growing attention to ecological impacts, the prevailing rationale remains predominantly anthropocentric, human-centred reasoning still prevails over ecosystem-centred reasoning. Consequently, the North Sea Foundation opts for 1) stronger ecosystem-based ecological standards for offshore wind parks, and 2) more strategic long-term monitoring (Interviewee 6). While the North Sea Coalition has made space to discuss these tensions, interviewees still note their worry that the scale-up the national government is aiming for might lead to unprecedented tipping-point effects on the ecosystem of the North Sea (Interviewee 6).

An emerging discourse around more-than-human / non-human justice of the North Sea

Since 2015, there has been increasing attention to the rights of nature. Inspired by a New Zealand River gaining legal status in 2015 to mitigate pollution, academic and artistic circles in the Netherlands became increasingly interested in a shift towards more-than-human and non-human justice. In 2015, the Embassy of the North Sea (NL: Ambassade van de Noordzee) was created to address these types of justice: *“The North Sea and life in the sea are their own. The Embassy of the North Sea was founded on this basis. Here we listen to the political voices of the things, plants, animals, microbes and people in and around the North Sea.”* (Over, n.d.) In the words of a landscape architect (Interviewee 7), who is affiliated with the Embassy of the North Sea: *“We forget that the sea is a landscape that already has residents.”* While the Embassy of the North Sea has gained traction in artistic circles, academia, and public media, and while they have a seat on the scientific council of the North Sea Coalition since ca. 2019, their participatory schemes with non- and more than human voices are still experimental and have not led to any concrete changes in regulation or governance regarding wind energy.

Summary

- The introduction of the **Climate Agreement** in 2019 brought significant changes to wind energy governance in the Netherlands and North Holland. The creation of **30 Regional Energy Strategies (RES) regions** restructured actor roles and shifted wind energy planning from the provincial level to a more participatory and justice-focused approach. These RES regions allowed local stakeholders to have a say in the designation of potential areas for wind and solar development.
- However, the **legal enforcement** of key principles, such as 50% local ownership, remains **pending**, and municipalities face challenges in adapting to their evolving roles in renewable energy development.
- In the meantime, **anti-onshore wind protests** led to a national push for offshore wind. To overcome contestation and friction around the use of the small North Sea, the national government instated the **North Sea Coalition**, a consensus-driven consultative body between stakeholders of the North Sea (fishery, marine, wind energy, oil/gas, etc).
- Overall, this period represents a phase with significant stakes, where renewable energy has become a focal point of government, citizen, and local organisation engagement. At the same time, it shows how a bigger **push for on/offshore wind results in more protest** and friction amongst citizens (onshore) and professional stakeholders (offshore).

Before provincial rules (pre-2012)

After provincial rules (2012), before RES formation (2019)

After RES formation (2019)

Figure 10. The planning process for the development of an onshore wind park in the Netherlands, divided into three time periods. Note that uninvited forms of participation are not included in the visualisation, but may still occur. Government actors are marked in green, market actors are marked in blue, and public actors are marked in grey. Sources: (Stuurgroep Regionale Energiestrategie, 2021; van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020a).

4.5 PHASE 3: ENERGY SECURITY AND OFFSHORE AMBITIONS (2022-2023)

Context and critical instance:

- The European **energy crisis** of 2022 marked a critical change in the development of wind energy, as it highlighted the **geopolitical risks of energy dependency**, resulting in a renewed interest in renewable energy to gain **energy security**. This changed the dominant narrative around wind energy: from wind energy being an intruder in the land- or seascape, to wind energy being an affordable and secure source of energy.
- In the meantime, **grid congestion** stalled onshore renewable energy projects, leading to an undershoot of the onshore wind energy development goals.
- These setbacks further spurred interest in **offshore** wind development, with the national government doubling offshore targets in 2022.

Energy crisis: exposed vulnerabilities

In 2022, the Netherlands faced a significant increase in energy prices. This energy crisis was brought on by several compounding influences. Firstly, the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022 resulted in a reduction of Russian natural gas imports to the EU by 80% in 2022 (Cozzi & Gould, 2022). This occurred on the heels of the phasing out of the Dutch domestic gas extraction from the Groningen gas fields, which had previously been the main source the Dutch energy production (Pure Energie, 2023). As a result, the energy crisis hit an import-dependent Netherlands hard, and in 2022, Dutch gas and electricity prices more than quadrupled in comparison to the year prior (CBS, 2023).

EU, NL and RES: more energy security through more renewables

As a response to rising energy prices, the EU and the Netherlands increased their renewable targets to achieve more energy resilience through local renewable energy production. The EU rolled out the 'REPowerEU' package in May 2022, which focused on, amongst others, creating energy resilience by "diversifying energy supplies" through renewable energy and locally supplied energy (European Commission, 2022). The REPowerEU program also increased the target share of renewable energy in the EU energy mix from 40% to 45% by 2030 (Chranioti et al., 2022). Likewise, the Netherlands scaled up its national climate goals from a 49% reduction in carbon emissions relative to 1990 to a 55-60% reduction in this period (Chranioti et al., 2022). Furthermore, while the RES 1.0 report was published in 2021 in North Holland, the discussion surrounding designated search areas was reopened to accommodate for interest in expanding search areas and increasing targets (Interviewee 5).

Public opinion: independence through renewables

Multiple interviewees remarked that the energy crisis led to increased interest in renewables by the public (Interviewees 1-5), with citizens ready to "*take matters into their own hands and ensure that we generate our own energy*" (interviewee 5). This interest in energy independence predominantly rose out of a need to rapidly reduce the cost of energy. In a study by the Dutch Central Statistical Office (CBS) and the Dutch Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO), this rise in prices led to an increase in energy poverty by 20% in 2022 in comparison to 2020¹ (Van der Sangen, 2023). According to Interviewee 4, the crisis in energy prices made renewable energy more attractive as a business case, as it became seen as the more dependable and economically viable option.

¹ This statistic only includes visible energy poverty. It is estimated that the actual statistic is higher, as invisible energy poverty is not included in this number. Invisible energy poverty concerns households not turning on the heating at all, to mitigate costs.

Undershoot of onshore wind development goals

Despite a notable shift in narratives and public sentiment towards embracing renewable energy in the Netherlands, the quantitative progress in onshore renewable energy development does not mirror this trend. The onshore renewable energy target for 2030 was set at 55 TWh (Chranioti et al., 2022). However, in 2022, Chranioti et al. projected a potential realisation of only 35-45 TWh by 2030, still surpassing the national target of 35 TWh (Figure 11).

While this may initially appear as positive progress as compared to the target of 35 TWh set in the RES, the report disclosed a significant drop in the number of projects initiated through the SDE++ subsidy scheme over the past three years, indicating a decline in subsidised projects (Figure 10). Consequently, the combined total of implemented and planned (pipeline) projects is projected to reach 31 TWh by 2030, falling short of the 35 TWh goal.

Figure 11. Estimation of 2030 renewable electricity production based on RES 1.0 reports (source: Chranioti et al., 2022).

Bottleneck in onshore wind development: grid congestion

One of the main bottlenecks of renewable energy is grid congestion: the electricity grid is not able to meet the varying loads of electricity caused by the different availabilities of wind and sun. This issue is poignant for the entire energy transition and not just wind and had been causing trouble for several years before this phase (i.e. described in Verkade and Hoffken, 2019). However, grid congestion is mentioned here, because it became an especially big bottleneck in the development of wind in North Holland around 2020. This was because of the connection of the Wieringermeer wind park in 2020, which took up nearly all remaining availability of the grid in the North Holland North RES region (Soeters, 2019) (see Figure 12). The local grid operator Liander was unprepared for this, resulting in several renewable energy projects in the region reporting unexpectedly long delays in connecting to the grid. This has dampened renewed interest in onshore wind energy development and increased pressure on grid operators to adapt to an altered energy landscape.

Figure 12. Grid capacity in North Holland, with red indicating no additional capacity, orange indicating no capacity available pending the outcome of grid expansions, and yellow indicating limited capacity (source: Netbeheer Nederland, 2023)

Offshore wind: upscaling and acceleration

In light of the growing interest in renewables and facing bottlenecks of onshore protests and grid congestion, the national government became increasingly interested in offshore wind. In 2022, the Dutch government announced its intention to double offshore wind development targets for 2030, adding an additional 10.7 GW to the previous goal of 11 GW (Bremmer & Nieuwenhuis, 2022). To facilitate this upscaling, the national government launched the national North Sea Programme (NL: Programma Noordzee 2022-2027). The task of the North Sea Programme was *“to find the right social balance in the spatial development of the North Sea. That development must be efficient and safe and fit within the preconditions of a healthy ecosystem”* (Programma Noordzee 2022-2027, n.d.).² The programme aimed to serve as the basis for allocating offshore wind development sites. The programme described a national ambition to realise 38 and 72 GW installed capacity of wind turbines by 2027 and 2050, respectively. The programme is based on several European directives, such as the Marine Strategy Framework (NL: Nederlandse Maritieme Strategie), as well as the Dutch Waterlaw (NL: Waterwet) and the North Sea Agreement (NL: Noordzeeakkoord 2021) and the North Sea Coalition (see Phase 2). The North Sea Programme includes a Community of Practice (CoP). This CoP consists of governments, entrepreneurs, research institutes, NGOs, and key industries. The goal of the CoP is to share practical knowledge and experience, stimulating innovation amongst professional organisations working on offshore wind and its intersections with other offshore transitions (i.e., food/protein, nature/ecology, etc) (Steins et al. 2021).

Summary

- This phase marked a critical turning point with the onset of the 2022 energy crisis. This crisis spurred a heightened awareness of energy dependency and led to an increased interest in renewables to create **energy security**, both at local and international levels.
- At the same time, **grid congestion** led to a stalling of onshore renewable projects in North Holland and other provinces. As a response, the national government turned to offshore wind development and doubled offshore targets. It underscored the importance of addressing **infrastructure bottlenecks** and **streamlining decision-making processes** to fully realize renewable energy goals in the region.

² Translated from Dutch, original: “De centrale opgave in het Programma Noordzee 2022–2027 is het vinden van de juiste maatschappelijke balans in de ruimtelijke ontwikkeling van de Noordzee. Die ontwikkeling moet efficiënt en veilig zijn en passen binnen de randvoorwaarden van een gezond ecosysteem.”

5 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

What types of procedures and processes have emerged and developed to be able to make decisions on where and how to build wind energy projects in North Holland?

In the Netherlands, a small and densely populated country, there is an ongoing **battle for space**. Therefore, site selection procedures for wind energy are geared at an efficient use of the landscape and **consensus-building** between conflicting interests. The following paragraphs elaborate on this in more detail.

Onshore: from ad-hoc private development to decentralised standardised governance

Since the inception of wind energy in the Netherlands, onshore wind development has become more standardised, decentralised, and more geared towards fair and inclusive site selection through bottom-up citizen participation. A key turning point that institutionalised these trends was the Regional Energy Strategies. These were introduced as part of the 2019 Dutch Climate Agreement, which was, in turn, a response to the international Paris Agreement of 2015. These strategies divided the country into regional energy strategy (RES) regions, which were then tasked with designating 'search areas' (NL: zoekgebieden) wherein wind energy projects were to be built, which could later be offered to developers. These areas were to be well suited for renewable energy and agreed upon by residents, municipalities, and local stakeholders. Before the RES regions, private developers were responsible for proposing projects and deciding where and how to build wind energy projects in North Holland. As such, the RES strategies shifted wind energy governance to a more **decentralised and standardised** approach, placing citizen involvement at the heart of site selection.

Offshore: from ad-hoc private development to national government leadership

Before 2013, private wind developers were responsible for the initiation and facilitation of the entirety of the offshore wind tendering process. Thus, the national government had no immediate control over the speed of development. The 2013 Energy Agreement marked a more active role for the government in developing offshore wind energy. It proposed a new tendering structure, in which the national government provided an all-inclusive package of wind farm, permit and installation. In doing so, it **centralised and standardised** offshore wind development.

In sum, both onshore and offshore wind have become increasingly **government-led and standardised** with increased recognition of the need for **deliberation and consensus** across a wide range of stakeholders (offshore) and citizens (onshore).

What have been key actors (and coalitions) and their activities and roles in the development of wind energy in North Holland?

The most important actors are the province, municipalities, the national government, the RES regions, citizens/local initiatives, and project developers. These paragraphs describe the role of the national, regional and local governments. For a discussion on RES and its role and activities, see the previous question. For a discussion on the role of citizens, see the following question.

Offshore: a strong national government seeking consensus

The national government has gained an increasingly important role in offshore wind energy development, orchestrating an all-in-one tender, wherein permits and development subsidies are offered within the same subsidy since the 2015 Offshore Wind Energy Act (NL: Wet windenergie op

zee) (Ministerie van Binnenlandse Zaken en Koninkrijksrelaties, 2023). In contrast, project developers have played an increasingly narrow role in the planning and tendering process, with tenders shaped by the national government prior to developer involvement. Project developers now are mainly involved in the execution of offshore wind parks and coordination with connecting to the onshore grid. The section on site selection (previous page) describes how this bigger role for the national government emerged out of the government's need for efficient use of the landscape.

From 2020 onwards, as a response to the increasing competition for sea space and associated conflicts between sectors, the national government instated a national consultative body between various stakeholders of the sea, called the North Sea Coalition (NL: Noordzeeoverleg). The North Sea Coalition created more space for **deliberation and consensus-finding** on issues regarding offshore site selection.

Onshore: a reluctant province under pressure from local actors

While, for offshore, the national government has become an increasingly important player, onshore power has become **increasingly decentralised**: ever since the Energy Agreement (2013), there has been a shift in responsibility towards **the province and, more recently, municipalities**, regarding the development of wind (see also Figure 10). However, this shift in roles did not go smoothly, as the province of North Holland proved itself a reluctant partner in advancing wind energy. The Energy agreement mandated 685.5 MW in newly installed capacity, which opposed North Holland's plan to curb wind energy development (van Zoelen, 2019). In response to these new goals and their new responsibility, the province adopted a reluctant approach, approving enough plans to reach the target, but doing nothing more, which in the end resulted in an undershoot of the 685.5 MW goal (van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020; van Zoelen, 2019). As described by Van Aalderen & Horlings (2020), the provincial government of North Holland approached this period with "authoritative reluctance", with a particular disinterest in local efforts or citizen initiatives (p. 9).

This reluctance created increasing tensions between the national and provincial governments. Moreover, it increased an **ongoing divide between urban and rural** positionings on wind development. Most opposition which fuelled the province's stance on wind energy development largely stemmed from rural areas. In contrast, urban centres, and particularly **the municipality of Amsterdam**, held more progressive values. Several **citizen initiatives** attempted to initiate new wind projects, and the city council's stance was pro-wind development within Amsterdam. However, efforts were hampered by the province, with an estimated 50 proposed projects turned down by the province during these years, resulting in a lull in wind energy development during this period (van Zoelen, 2019). This resulted in frustration regarding the uniform governance applied to the province, which urban residents felt prioritised rural agendas (van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020).

On the other hand, the creation of the RES regions has shifted responsibility further towards **municipalities** and away from the province. This shift has been similarly bumpy as in particular smaller municipalities are not equipped to take on greater responsibility in renewable energy planning. Throughout this process, the role of project developers has similarly narrowed in relation to site selection and planning, which is now orchestrated by a wide range of stakeholders through the **RES search areas**. Project developers are invited to propose wind turbine or park specifications in specific search areas and under certain conditions, including 50% local ownership and a focus on community participation and justice. This has reduced developers' role in some aspects, yet expanded it in others as greater intentionality and local consideration are likely required in order to abide by RES principles in North Holland.

What roles have local residents played within these procedures and processes?

As described in previous sections, the role of residents in **onshore wind energy** has become increasingly **powerful and institutionalised**. Contrastingly, for offshore, residents are increasingly less involved in these procedures and processes. The following sections describe this dichotomy in more detail.

Onshore: from protest to a seat at the table

Local residents have become increasingly involved in wind development. Their involvement diversified over the years: from **protest and opposition** (ca. 2010-2015 through Wind Alarm and the Wieringermeer protests) to an increasing **seat at the table** in formal decision-making processes around site selection (ca. 2019 onwards). Policies and governance arrangements increasingly took citizens along in the early stages of the wind development, rather than after the fact, or not at all. This is characterised by the RES policy of the 2019 Climate Agreement, in which citizens were asked to play a vital part in informing where wind was to be built in their region (see first section of this chapter).

This trend of citizens becoming increasingly formally and professionally involved in wind occurred within a wider political landscape promoting participation and citizen involvement around 2010. At the time, a discourse emerged that promoted citizen participation, characterised by the phrase coined by the King's throne speech at the time, which spoke of the **participation society** (NL: participatiemaatschappij). In this participation society, citizens and volunteers were to take on more responsibility to manage certain societal systems (i.e. as informal caretakers) (Fraaije et al., 2021). The participation society was a product of years of austerity governance in public policy, after the recession caused by the financial crisis of 2008 (Fraaije et al., 2021).

In the energy transition, this notion of the importance of participation was reflected by the scaling-up and recognition of the **importance of community energy**. Citizens started to become increasingly involved in the energy system, and the concept of **prosumer** (an energy-consuming and -producing citizen) became more widely recognised in public policy. This professionalisation of the citizen as a prosumer became formally acknowledged through the 2013 Energy Agreement. This agreement institutionalised the importance of citizen cooperatives and local electricity consumption and production systems. The Energy Agreement marked a new period of a steep increase in citizen (financial) participation in the energy transition as a whole, including wind energy (Fraaije et al., 2021). In 2017, more than 80% of the wind turbines developed in the Netherlands invited a form of citizen participation (van Aalderen & Horlings, 2020).

Offshore: from protest to lack of engagement

Unlike onshore wind, there is little involvement of residents in offshore wind development. This can be explained by multiple reasons. Firstly, significant cost reductions in offshore wind have allowed offshore wind development further away from shore. This places wind parks out of sight of citizens, leading to a decrease in the amount of offshore wind protests. In the period 1990-2015, offshore wind was still too expensive to build further from the shore, and thus projects that were developed were built in near-shore areas. This resulted in conflicts with residents wanting to protect the shoreline from so-called 'horizon pollution' (NL: horizonvervuiling), such as a conflict in 2016 where residents protested against an offshore wind park 20 km away from the shore, instead demanding a distance of 60 km (West, 2016). In the meantime, far offshore wind had become attractive to the national government, which wanted to meet climate goals and international climate agreements with efficient

and now affordable offshore wind. Moreover, far offshore wind would allow them to avoid issues with opposition and acceptance from residents around onshore wind development.

While in recent years onshore wind has become increasingly citizen-led and citizen-owned through financial participation models and community-led initiatives, offshore wind is mostly developed by professional stakeholders. As described by Bezeij (2017), this is because offshore wind projects are large and complex, with very high investments that require capacity and skills that community-led initiatives might not have. Moreover, tendering structures are not oriented toward citizen participation.

How have regulatory institutions (e.g. regulations, legal developments) shaped the development of wind energy over time and space in North Holland?

Delays in the National Energy Act

Since the liberalisation of the Dutch energy market in 1998 through the Electricity and Gas Law, this regulation has yet to be updated, even though this has been promised by the national government in recent years. The new Energy Act (NL: Energiewet), under the Clean Energy Package, was set to be instituted in 2021 but has since been delayed. The act aims to merge the previously separate gas and electricity acts as these two systems are increasingly overlapping and becoming interdependent. In addition, the new law will incorporate sustainability goals required from national and EU levels, and support an energy system in transition. The delay in the rollout of this new energy regulation has led to **frustration amongst developers and deceleration of sustainable energy advancement** in recent years: *“We had a project [which aimed to improve energy efficiency] in 2017, which didn’t happen - a collaboration with the grid operator - because they [the grid operator] said that the new energy law would not allow the plans of the project [...] Now we are five to six years later, and that new energy law is still not here”* (Interviewee 1). In the words of Interviewee 3: *“the lack of regulation is a big bottleneck at the moment. That is a big decelerator, because no one knows where they stand.”* Some municipalities are not granting any onshore building permits, because they are waiting for potentially new national regulation (Chranioti et al., 2022). The draft Energy Act was submitted to the Council of State in 2022, and is now undergoing further revisions (Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat, 2023).

New Environmental Act

Similarly, an updated environmental act (NL: Omgevingswet) for the Netherlands has been delayed for several years. The Environmental Act is necessary for the **legal binding of RES strategies** including the baseline of 50% local ownership for onshore wind and solar projects. The Environmental Act has now been passed and will come into effect in January 2024. Its implementation is set to solidify the growing roles of municipalities in implementing RES plans. In addition, it is hoped that the act will alleviate some of the legal bottlenecks highlighted in the Monitor RES report (Chranioti et al., 2022).

Offshore Wind Energy Act

While the overarching electricity and gas law has not changed, in 2015, an act was introduced around offshore wind energy: the Offshore Wind Energy Act (Regels Omtrent Windenergie Op Zee (Wet Windenergie Op Zee), 2014). This law stipulated the **new and larger role of the national government** in offshore wind development. It created coherence between locations, permits and subsidies. This

built upon the restructuring of offshore wind energy development roles initiated by the Energy Agreement (see Figure 9).

Influence of EU mandates

While regulations and legal developments have often been delayed in adjusting and backing targets and ambitions, the European Union is placing increasing pressure on member countries to change regulatory institutions accordingly. In 2020, each member state was required to submit a National Energy and Climate plan, which detailed plans for the energy transition and mitigating climate change over 10 years. Following the submission of these plans, the EU increasingly requires legal backing for plans.

How have normative and cultural-cognitive institutions shaped the development of wind energy over time and space in North Holland?

Wind energy as a national symbol of innovation and progress

Ever since the 15th century, windmills have been a symbol of the Dutch tendency to model, adjust, and organise landscapes and nature in a way to harness economic prosperity. In the 15th century, the first Dutch wind turbine created the first polders. These diked former marshlands, also known as 'droogmakerijen', became key to the Dutch landscape. North Holland became especially known for its man-made polder landscapes. The Beemster area, for example, was dried in 1612 and was kept dry by 50 windmills for more than 300 years. Windmills are thus part of the cultural heritage of the Netherlands, demonstrating the Dutch drive for innovation and progress.

Wind energy as a symbol of climate change mitigation

In the 1990s, as a response to the first IPCC report, energy became tied to climate change in the public debate. As a consequence, wind energy started to be framed as a solution to environmental unsustainability (Kooij, Oteman, et al., 2018, p. 56-57).

Wind energy as a threat to cultural landscapes

While in urban areas such as Amsterdam and Haarlem, wind turbines were seen as a solution against climate change, rural residents and the Province of North Holland generally remained contrary to building wind on land (see previous section on the role of the province). They considered wind turbines to pollute the cultural identity of the landscape and protested the building of new wind farms.

What role has the notion of energy justice and energy sovereignty played in the development of wind energy in North Holland?

Initially, during the phase of the 2013 Energy Agreement, energy justice played a limited and more implicit role. The focus was primarily on meeting renewable energy targets. This top-down approach led to tensions between the national and provincial government and a divide between urban and rural positions on wind development. Public opinion regarding onshore wind was generally negative, leading to protests and resistance.

In the subsequent phase, with the formation of the RES regions and the introduction of the Klimaatakkoord, participation became a cornerstone of Dutch energy governance. This led to a heightened perception and valuation of **procedural justice** and **intergenerational justice**, which were

actively considered in the drafting of the climate agreement, acknowledging the need for fair processes and the long-term impacts on future generations. As a result, the emphasis shifted towards a bottom-up, participatory approach, where local communities and municipalities were actively involved in wind energy planning. The designation of search areas and increased engagement aimed to address public opposition and include residents in decision-making processes. While efforts have been made to make decision-making more inclusive, current regulations favour those with the financial means to invest in renewable energy, leaving out individuals who cannot afford such investments (Interviewee 1). For instance, energy cooperatives often have membership fees, or while subsidies are available for local cooperatives, up-front costs still stand. Governance procedures emphasise fairness of decision-making processes, including appropriate participation, access to information, respectful treatment, and unbiased decision-making (Interviewees 2 and 3). While onshore wind energy has thus been increasingly geared at involving residents, offshore wind lacks citizen engagement. With wind projections for the future focusing mainly on (far) offshore areas, the risk is that wind energy will become **depoliticised** and take place mainly outside of the public sphere (Blues & Gailing, 2016).

The 2022-2023 energy crisis put aspects around **distributional justice** higher on the political agenda. The crisis, caused by geopolitical events (such as the invasion of Russia into Ukraine) and grid congestion, led to price shocks and increased energy independence and poverty concerns. These concerns were heightened because of the phase-out of the domestic Groningen Gas due to earthquakes resulting from gas extraction. The need to address these issues and mitigate the impacts on vulnerable communities emphasised the importance of energy justice considerations in wind energy development. The discourse and narrative surrounding wind energy changed, shifting the dialogue towards meeting the needs of marginalised communities. Financial participation has been found as a method to comply with this need for a fairer distribution of costs and benefits (Interviewee 4). One concern is that the acceleration of offshore wind leaves less room for citizens to benefit from local projects, as financial participation in offshore projects is yet to be on the table. As such, offshore wind profits go to large (foreign) investors, rather than the Dutch population through i.e. cooperative ownership models, as has become more common on land (Koops & van Zoelen, 2021)).

Lastly, frustrations around **recognition justice** can be traced in the protests against the **uniformity of regulation** and the large rural/urban divide in the Province. This is characteristic of the province, as it is starkly divided into Amsterdam, the capital and largest city of the country, and everything else, which is mostly rural. This large divide has led to frustrations amongst the various municipalities about provincial regulation. For example, the municipality of Amsterdam has felt frustrated with the province as they feel they are treated as if they were another rural municipality (see also paragraphs on the role of the province). Van Aalderen & Horlings (2020) state that *"even though their [provincial] strategy focuses on protecting the inhabitants of the province from nuisance, a repeated critique voiced the uniformity of the strategy: No difference was made in the strict regulations between urban and rural landscapes, or between types of initiatives,"* referring to the provincial strategy of North Holland (p.10).

While ecologists and NGOs have shared concerns about the lack of long-term thinking or monitoring of the cumulative effects of wind development on the ecosystem, especially at sea (Interviewees, 6, 7, and 8), aspects of **more than- and non-human justice** are gaining traction in the discourse on wind development. This shift in discourse includes 1) stricter regulations to protect species from wind turbines, 2) attempts at reframing the concept of 'residents' to include non-human / more-than-

human entities, and 3) attempts to give the North Sea legal rights (for the last two points, see also the discussion on the role of residents). From the end of 2023, wind turbines will be regulated to two rotations per minute maximum in the evening during times of mass bird migration. This measure was created by Rijkswaterstaat (Department of Waterways and Public Works) in cooperation with wind park owners, Tennet (TSO), the Ministry of Agriculture, Nature and Food Quality, bird protection, and the North Sea Foundation.

6 SYNTHESIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Historically, North Holland has seen the emergence of onshore wind energy installations aimed at swiftly and efficiently achieving renewable energy targets. However, strong local opposition quickly highlighted the ineffectiveness of rapid scale-up that fails to consider local voices and interests. These contestations encouraged the restructuring of renewable energy policy – the Regional Energy Strategies (RES) – with increased avenues for citizen involvement, leading governments (local, regional, and national) to include **citizen participation as a guiding principle** for onshore wind energy development. The RES took a decentralised approach, allowing each region to set targets and design a locally suitable split between solar and wind energy. While a relatively balanced split is optimal from a technical perspective, onshore wind only makes up about 10% of RES plans in North Holland.

To reach its goal of independence from Russian and Groningen gas, as well as meet national and international climate mitigation goals, the Netherlands needs continued and accelerated renewable energy development. Resistance towards further onshore wind development, combined with advances in offshore wind technology, has **turned the Dutch government's attention toward the North Sea**, with offshore wind targets doubling in 2022 to 21 GW of installed capacity by 2030. Such an acceleration does not come without risks, an important one being the risk that installing wind becomes the goal itself instead of a means to an end – a reliable, renewables-based energy system.

Our research shows that the discourse in the Netherlands around wind energy development has become focused on justice and participation onshore, yet increasingly **techno-optimist** regarding offshore wind. The development of onshore wind energy has seen large efforts towards increasing the participation of citizens, a more just distribution of benefits, and open and inclusive decision-making models through the RES. On the other hand, **offshore wind has yet to incorporate the lessons of onshore wind development**, which highlight the importance of citizen participation and the consideration of 'local' impacts. These lessons underscore the importance of engaging a diverse array of stakeholders, as taking all perspectives into account can lead to a more comprehensive understanding of both present and future risks and their repercussions. The North Sea Coalition brings many stakeholders to the table, but has more work ahead on questions such as the just distribution of impacts, and the potential to engage those onshore in offshore wind implementation. Doing so may not only offer insights into effective mitigation strategies but also foster innovative approaches to the energy transition such as the exploration of alternative socio-economic models.

The following paragraphs describe two prominent challenges and associated risks that arise from the current approach to wind energy development in North Holland and the Netherlands. Based on input from our interviewees and our analysis, we provide recommendations to tackle these challenges.

Challenge: Making ecosystem health a key factor in wind development decisions

Currently, there is limited knowledge of the cumulative biological effects of offshore wind development on the North Sea. Scientists have warned that a massive scale-up of turbines may trigger important ecological tipping points (Interviewees 6 and 8). Yet, the national government opts to push forward ambitious wind energy plans in the North Sea, bypassing warnings to meet ambitious climate goals (Interviewees 6, 7, and 8). This highlights a delicate balance that needs to be tackled: reducing carbon emissions through the energy transition while keeping ecosystems intact.

Our **recommendations** are:

- 1) Create an open access knowledge base: Commit to **long-term monitoring of ecological impacts** of offshore wind energy, exchange data and insights among stakeholders, and collectively learn about the impacts and risks involved and strategies to address them.
- 2) Consider the **sea as a populated landscape with more-than-human residents** (such as marine life and ecosystems) and invest in ways to make their interests part of the decision-making process.

Challenge: Engaging the public in offshore wind development

Contestations and protests around onshore wind energy development have sparked new approaches to participation in decision-making, new perspectives on wind development, and innovative ownership models. Still, these approaches are limited in their effectiveness due to a lack of clarity and enforcement in participation schemes. In contrast, offshore wind development seems an increasingly depolitical endeavour managed by the national government based on data-driven models prioritising maximum return on investment and technological efficiency (instead of balancing this with local benefit or ecosystem development). Now that offshore wind development is on the rise both in the Netherlands and the EU, the challenge is to engage the public in the transition, rather than leaving decision-making in wind energy development solely to technocrats. This necessitates posing critical questions as we shape policies – who should have a say in development, and how should the benefits and burdens be distributed? The Dutch energy transition provides the opportunity to tackle unfair distributions of impacts: a chance to come up with innovative ownership models and scale up citizen-led decision-making, as well as factor more-than-human agents into the equation.

Our **recommendations** are:

- 1) **Build capacity** (i.e. skills, resources) in community energy organisations, as well as local and regional governments, to create a level playing field with international developers in the complex endeavour of onshore and offshore wind farm development.
- 2) **Enforce community decision-making and financial benefits** in onshore wind park permits **through legal measures** in order to mandate and clarify roles and regulations. In doing so, provide clear definitions of participation and local ownership. Similarly, **offshore tendering** procedures should adapt to stimulate community participation and ownership, connecting to community-based actors.

In addition to these challenge-specific recommendations, we provide two **overarching recommendations** for wind energy development in the Netherlands:

- 1) Keep sight of the overall goal of a habitable planet for all species, balancing both keeping ecosystems intact and renewable energy development. By doing so, we avoid narrowing our attention to a single technology, such as (offshore) wind energy development. Instead, provide space and resources for innovators to experiment with **a diversity of transition pathways**. This includes seeking potential synergies, such as combining the development of renewables with energy sufficiency (i.e. shared mobility, post-capitalism and de-growth pathways), and investigating alternative business and organisational models.
- 2) Create **reflexive governance structures** that allow for reflection, learning, and action on the points mentioned above. Specifically, reflexively monitor RES projects throughout their process, evaluating whether justice (procedural, distributive, recognition) and participation have been included in the process and implemented.

ANNEX 1: BIBLIOGRAPHY

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ANNEX 2: INTERVIEWEES

Interviewee	Name	Date	Duration
1	Aernoud Olde, coordinator Energie Samen (Energy Together) North Holland	08-05-23	90 mins
2	Programme manager North Holland South Regional Energy Strategy	31-05-23	60 mins
3	Regional Energy Strategies coordinator of North Holland	31-05-23	60 mins
4	Marco Berkhout, sector manager energy transition at the Province North Holland	06-06-23	90 mins
5	Sijas Akkerman, director Nature and Environmental Federation North Holland (Natuur en Milieufederatie Noord-Holland)	16-06-23	60 mins
6	Projectlead nature-friendly offshore energy/marine ecologist – North Sea Foundation	22-08-23	60 mins
7	Ziege van den Berk, landscape architect and researcher at MUST and the Embassy of the North Sea	03-10-23	60 mins
8	Han Lindeboom, Emeritus professor Marine Ecology, Wageningen University	17-10-23	60 mins

ANNEX 3: DEDUCTIVE CODES

	'Main' code name	Code description	Why this code? Relation to RQs	Subcodes
1	Timeline	Historical data: key 'events', instances or phases (in the broadest sense of the word) incl. dates and involved actors – higher level code	RQ1a; Code exists so that we can construct the timeline and historical account	1.1 Pre-period (pre-2013) 1.2 Focus period (2013-2023)
2	Critical instance(s) of change	Data to write up critical instances of change – higher level code	RQ1-4 Code exists so that critical instance can be identified and written up – codes below provide more detail	
3	Wind energy governance actors: aims, interests, values, beliefs	Description of wind energy governance actors along: name, aims, interests, values, beliefs	RQ2b Code exists to understand the actors involved and their interests and drivers & overall thought patterns and normative perspectives	
4	Wind energy governance actors: roles & activities	Description of wind energy governance actors along: name, their 'assigned' roles, and (wind energy and other) activities. We are particular interested in activities that attempt to change (or in other ways co-shape) existing institutions such as regulations, social norms, etc. or procedures and processes	RQ1b, 2a, 3c, 4d Code exists so that we can describe the different wind energy governance actors (along different parameters), identify potential interviewees. Consider that actors can include human and more than human actors.	4.1 State/government actors 4.2 Market/business actors 4.3 Not-for-profit actors (NGO, associations, etc) 4.4 Community actors (residents, energy cooperatives, neighborhoods, unorganized)
5	More than human actors and their role in governance arrangements	Descriptions of the role of more than human actors (plants, birds, grids, etc.) in wind energy governance arrangements	RQ1b, 2a, 3c, 4d Code exists so that we can describe the different wind energy governance actors – It might double up with code 4 but it still exists to pay particular attention to these types of actors	5.1 Living organisms 5.2 Infrastructure 5.3 Other

6	Wind energy governance actors: narratives/discourses	Descriptions of 'wind energy' narratives (i.e. what is 'wrong', what is an 'alternative')	RQ1d; (RQ2d) Code exists so that we can better understand changing narrative and discourses over time	
7	Wind energy governance actors coalitions and networks: Interactions/relations between them and their shared activities and narratives	Descriptions of interactions as well as formal & informal relations/networks between wind energy governance actors (what, how) & what have been shared activities and narratives. We are particularly interested in activities that attempt to change existing institutions such as regulations, social norms, etc.	RQ1b; 2c, 2d Code exists so that we can better understand the governance arrangements – this includes human and more than human factors	
8	Wind energy contestations, discussions and points of disagreement	Descriptions of contestations e.g. disagreements about aims and the future of wind energy, approaches to lobbying policymakers, etc.	RQ2e Code exists because we want to better understand the 'breaking points' of wind energy development or conflicts in governance arrangements	
9	Power relations	Description of actors having power over one another, having different kinds of power (e.g. transformative, hierarchical, etc.) or joining forces	RQ5c Code exists to understand the extent to which power relations in energy systems are changing/reproducing	
10	Key regulations & legal developments – institutions	Descriptions of key EU, national and regional, local changes to regulations and legal changes that influenced wind energy in the regions	RQ1c; RQ4a Code exists to understand regulative institutions	
11	Key social, economic and/or ecological developments – institutions	Descriptions of key EU, national and regional, local changes to social, economic and ecological developments that influenced wind energy in the regions	RQ4b Code exists to understand different types of developments shaping wind energy	
12	Values, norms, and beliefs – institutions	Descriptions of key EU, national and regional, local changes to values, social norms and beliefs that influenced wind energy in the regions	RQ1e; RQ4c Code exists to understand cultural-cognitive and normative institutions	

13	Planning & project management procedures and processes i.e. governance processes and procedures	Descriptions of planning & project management procedures and processes (who, what, how, with whom, etc) – changes over time	RQ3a; RQ3c Code exists to gain an understanding of the different procedures and processes around wind energy development and deployment (and their effectiveness) and who shapes these	
14	Participatory practices and processes: Forms & types	Descriptions of participatory practices and processes (who, what, how, with whom, etc.) – changes over time	RQ3b; RQ3d Code exists to gain an understanding of the variety of participatory practices and processes used by whom, how and for what	14.1 Realized examples of participatory practices 14.2 Theoretical/recommended participatory practices
15	Participatory practices and processes: lived experience & their role in co-shaping wind energy	Descriptions of the role of participatory practices and processes (incl. unwanted, uninvited, alternative) in wind energy development and of the lived experience of those processes	RQ3b; RQ3d Code exists to understand how different types of participatory practices and processes are experienced by different actors, and the role that they play in co-shaping wind energy development and deployment	
16	Types of issues of justice: Framings, narratives, discussions	Descriptions of how issues of justice are framed and/or discussed (explicit and implicit ways) by individual and/ or groups of actors	RQ5a Code exists to understand how issues of justice are being framed (e.g. access to affordable energy)	
17	Justice and/or sovereignty: practices	Descriptions of how justice and/or sovereignty issues are understood and/or practiced (or not) by individual and/ or groups of actors	RQ5b Code exists to understand how justice and/or sovereignty are being understood and/or practiced	
18	18. Questions, uncertainties, concerns			
19	Recommendations			

ANNEX 4: MEETINGS AND EVENTS ATTENDED

1. NEST Webinar: Regional Energy Transitions – March 23rd, 2023
2. SIET Webinar: Dutch Policy for Future Citizen Participation – March 10th, 2023